

**Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability
of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through
Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge
Solutions' Gains**

**D3.3: System integration and dry-run testing feedback report
(1st version)**

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
4G	4th Generation mobile network
5G	5th Generation mobile network
AI	Artificial intelligence
API	Application programming interface
BS	Base station
CC	Compute continuum
CPU	Central processing unit
DL	Downlink
E2E	End-to-end
FPS	Frames per second
FWA	Fixed wireless access
GEO	Geostationary earth orbit
GPU	Graphics processing unit
HW	Hardware
ISP	Internet service provider
KFT	Knowledge facilitation tool
KPI	Key performance indicator
LEO	Low earth orbit
LoRaWAN	Long range wide area network
LoS	Line of sight
MEO	Medium earth orbit
mmWave	Millimeter wave
NAS	Network-attached storage
NR	New radio
NIC	Network interface card
NUC	Next unit of computing
OAI	Open air interface
PtMP	Point-to-multipoint
PtP	Point-to-point

RAM	Random access memory
RAN	Radio access network
RTT	Round-trip time
SBC	Single board computer
SW	Software
TC	Test case
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
UC	Use case
UE	User equipment
UGV	Unmanned ground vehicle
UL	Uplink
Wi-Fi	Wireless fidelity

1 Executive Summary

The XGain project seeks to provide access to smart XG, last-mile connectivity, and edge computing solutions for relevant stakeholders such as municipalities, policymakers, farmers, foresters and their associations by fostering sustainable and inclusive development in rural, coastal, and sub-urban areas. The development of a knowledge facilitation tool (KFT) is the project's objective. This tool will be used to support decision-making by the relevant stakeholders when selecting technology ecosystems that enhance their regions in various ways, such as minimisation of energy consumption and reduction of digital inequalities among people.

The purpose of this deliverable in its first version is to provide 'isolated' measurements about technical key performance indicators (KPIs) for different last mile connectivity technologies and edge processing solutions in laboratory environments. The Partners participating in the six use cases (UCs), with the infrastructure and equipment that are available at the time of writing this deliverable, have provided these measurements. The execution of the testing and evaluation procedures, presented in detail in the following sections, requires appropriate software (SW) and hardware (HW) that is also provided.

The technologies examined in this dry-run testing originate from the pool of communication and computation technologies described in D3.1: 'Technology and edge processing enablers, and service processing optimisation solutions (1st version)' considering in parallel also the UCs' equipment identified in D5.1: 'Planning and setup handbook, and operational management report (1st version)'. Hence, measurements of the technologies that are intended to be used in the pilots, and also for other communication and computation devices collected in the stocktaking process for the KFT, are presented. In the next version of this deliverable, the 'isolated' devices will be connected to end-to-end (E2E) configurations and the KPIs will be measured for integrated configurations.

2 Introduction

This deliverable provides isolated KPI measurements in different laboratory environments related to the UCs. These measurements are based on the connectivity and computational technologies. Various processing enablers (that can be applied in different compute continuum (CC) layers, i.e., extreme/far/near zones) and network devices related with radio access network (RAN) and transport/backhaul layers, are tested. These are provided by 8 different Partners of XGain, i.e., ICCS, CAPTAIN, ICOM, I2CAT, CAFA, BENCO, ASTRO and ART21, based on their equipment and expertise. Moreover, considering that EVILVO has not appropriate infrastructure, it does not participate in this dry run testing. The ‘isolated’ term means that the network and computation devices will be tested separately and different technical KPIs such as resource utilisation, processing time and network throughput/latency will be provided. However, in the next phase of Task 3.4 the ‘isolated’ devices will be integrated and E2E measurements will be done.

Additionally, except from private network infrastructures, public networks’ measurements that are meaningful for KFT, are also provided. Testing public cellular networks, especially 4th generation mobile network (4G) and 5th generation mobile network (5G), within XGain it is essential to understand their performance and reliability in rural settings, where infrastructure and signal propagation challenges are distinct from urban environments. Considering that the Spanish laboratory is located in a rural environment, the pilot in Spain is chosen for the evaluations. Evaluating the performance of outdoor cellular networks can provide valuable insights into the real-world capabilities of current cellular technologies in regions that often face connectivity disparities. While these measurements are not directly related to the Spanish pilot to be deployed on-site, where a private cellular network is used, the evaluations will serve a bigger purpose by shedding light on potential bottlenecks, guiding infrastructure improvements, and shaping future rural connectivity strategies for broader deployments or services that might just rely on this type of connectivity.

2.1 Mapping XGain Outputs

Table 1: Adherence to XGain GA deliverable & tasks description.

XGain GA Component Title	XGain GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D3.3 System integration and dry-run testing feedback report			
Initial report on the integrated and tested technological solutions delivered			
TASKS			
Task 3.4 - System Integration and Dry-run Testing in Lab Environment	T3.4 will focus on the realisation of the resulting technology mixtures, for later validation in WP5. This will include agile system integration and testing cycles, where (i)	Sections 3-7	Each section provides a detailed analysis of UCs’ dry-run testing, including of isolated connectivity and computation technologies measurements.

<p>connectivity and processing infrastructure components will be integrated and tested, (ii) support software stacks/platforms will be deployed and tested e.g., virtualisation platforms, service orchestration platforms, etc. through system integration, and (iii) application/service software will be deployed and thoroughly tested. This activity will enable then the end-to-end testing and validation of the technology mixtures selected for individual environments, prior to eventual deployment in the field (WP5).</p>		
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2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable presents the isolated measurements of different connectivity and computation technologies in laboratory under the Task 3.4 ‘System Integration and Dry-run Testing in Lab Environment’. It serves as an initial report of D3.3 in Month 15 and will be complemented and enhanced by a second deliverable (Version 2) which will be reported in Month 27.

In terms of deliverable’s structure, each UC after a brief description of the supported service to make the connection of measurements with UCs’ scope, depicts the relevant KPIs and the measurements either in terms of diagrams or tables. For each testing scenario a detailed technical description is made including the used equipment.

More specifically the document is logically divided into 5 main sections based on the different UCs that participate in dry-run testing. Each UC section includes the same sub-sections, but with different content according to the specific UC. The structure of each section is as follows:

- 1) Overview of the service that is provided by each UC
- 2) Description of laboratory testing framework including:
 - a. Overall presentation of testing scenarios
 - b. The KPIs that are measured and are related with the radio access network, the transport network, and the computing segments that are parts of the KFT. In general, latency (network or processing), throughput, jitter and resource utilisation are the used KPIs in this phase of Task

3.4, based on UCs' scope and available equipment. Specifically, for each KPI the related segment, its description and measuring process are provided. In terms of segment, we encode the 2 different parts of connectivity technologies and computation technologies as "Conn" and "Comp" respectively. Thus, if one KPI includes one or both types of devices we write in the segment column "Conn"/ "Comp" or "Conn-Comp" respectively.

c. Detailed description of tested cases with the corresponding measurement results

3) Conclusions extracted by testing procedure

3 UC 1: Rural Community Services (Spain)

3.1 Overview of the Service Supported by UC

Drones, whether airborne or on the ground, are essential for tasks like surveillance, delivery, disaster management, and more. In rural settings, they are invaluable for tasks like real-time crop monitoring, pest detection, and area surveillance. Traditional communication methods, like Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi), cannot support the real-time, high-performance demands of drones. Instead, 5G technology can provide the high throughput, low latency, and reliability needed for high-resolution video and sensor data. Beyond tech, drone users need dedicated rural spaces, compliant with local regulations, for training and evaluations. This underscores the need for both a physical testing area and a robust 5G network infrastructure for drone services. A representative scenario that is yet to be determined and that is typical for drone operations, will be punctually deployed in the 5G testbed in Mora la Nova, Spain.

3.2 Lab Testing Framework

3.2.1 Testing Scenarios

One or more drones will be deployed at the pilot site and linked via 5G to a local emulated “operations centre”. For bringing and deploying such drones, an external drone operator company is responsible. The necessary equipment (drones, application server if required, etc.) will be brought by them to the testbed for the pilot execution. The drone company offers services like live video monitoring, aided by video/image processing. We take this scenario as a reference for the planning of pilot activities, which are being refined as per Task 5.2 activities. The 5G connection of the testbed, known for its high bandwidth, minimal latency, and reliability, will support the drone operations. The execution of the tests will be either indoor or outdoor, for both environments’ connectivity will be available. For this scenario to work, a comprehensive 5G network, including a drone (5G user equipment (UE)), a 5G base station functioning at 3.9 GHz and a virtualized 5G core will be set up, complemented by edge-computing capabilities.

The full infrastructure available in the i2CAT testbed is depicted in Figure 1, showing the elements that will be used during the pilot, and additionally the elements that will be used for separate technology validations. Overall, 3 access networks (4G/5G and Wi-Fi5) are available, 3 transport networks (millimeterwave (mmWave) backhauling over 60, 70, and 80 GHz), and two compute tiers, namely near edge and far edge, are deployed in two locations: the warehouse, and the regional council. The 4G/5G in- and outdoor standalone cells are deployed inside and in the immediate vicinity of the warehouse, respectively, next to dedicated compute nodes as part of the near edge. The small cells are standalone devices from Cablefree that only require to be connected to a 4G or 5G core over an ethernet or fibre connection to enable end user connectivity. Since these small cells are used to create a private 5G standalone network, dedicated spectrum is required. The Spanish ministry grants spectrum for research purposes, as it is the case in XGain. Normally, 40 MHz are granted, located in the n77 5G band. For the XGain project, this spectrum will be requested for the technology testing periods and for the pilot execution. For the time being, the Cablefree devices are not yet available. To still be able to perform dry-lab testing with private 4G/5G networks in the first testing phase, we use a setup based on an Amarisoft Callbox³, which uses the same underlying solution that is integrated in Cablefree.

³ <https://www.amarisoft.com/products/test-measurements/amari-lte-callbox/>

Figure 1: Overall testbed located in Mora la Nova/Mora d'Ebre (i2CAT).

The warehouse is connected to the regional council over a Siklu⁴ 80 GHz point-to-point (PtP) link of around 3.5 Km of length with a maximum capacity of 10 Gbps (full duplex). In the regional council the near edge compute node is hosted. Note that both edge compute nodes are connected to each other and are governed by an OpenStack deployment that allows the deployment of services at either location. In addition to the nodes that are installed as part of the fixed infrastructure, i2CAT will deploy two additional types of nodes that are now in the Barcelona laboratory and will be hosted in the warehouse. The goal is to provide a wider range of computing devices to be analysed. The two types of nodes are Raspberry Pi4 and Intel next unit of computing (NUC), compact devices used for light- to medium-weight computing services. The technical specifications of the two classes of computing nodes are as follows:

- Near Edge:
 - Intel NUC 11: Intel NUC11PAHi5 Barebone i5-1135G7, 2.4 GHz - 4.2 GHz
 - CPU: 4 cores. 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-1135G7 @ 2.40GHz
 - RAM: 8GB SODIMM DDR4 Synchronous 2667 MHz
 - Disk: SSD 500GB
- Far Edge:
 - Raspberry Pi 4 Model B:
 - CPU: 4 cores. Broadcom BCM2711, Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @1.8GHz

⁴ <https://www.siklu.com/>

- RAM: 8GB
- Disk: MicroSD 64GB CL10

Finally, the water treatment plant is connected to the warehouse over a 60 GHz point-to-multipoint (PtMP) link and a 70 GHz PtP link, both based on Siklu technology. Both links are around 300 m long and offer an aggregate nominal capacity of 1 Gbps each (half-duplex). At the water treatment plant, 2 Wi-Fi nodes are deployed that provide users with Wi-Fi access towards the edge computing infrastructure in the warehouse. The Wi-Fi nodes are two Gateworks⁵ single-board computers equipped each with a dedicated Wi-Fi interface, configured to operate with an 80 MHz bandwidth channel in the 5 GHz band.

Not shown in the topology are the locally available 4G and 5G public networks that also can be used for characterisation of rural 4G/5G connectivity. It should be noted that the connectivity is measured inside or close to the warehouse or at the water treatment plant. The reason for not including measurements at the regional council, is because the regional council is located very close to cellular base stations, making this location less representative for rural environment where cellular base stations can be up to several kilometres away from the location where a service is to be deployed.

For the testing performed within the Task 3.4 activities, the different segments present in this overall testbed will be evaluated: The 4G/5G and Wi-Fi radio access networks, the wireless mmWave transport links and the near and far edge computing devices.

Figure 2: Pilot setup diagram (i2CAT).

Figure 2 on the other hand shows the planned pilot setup, that only uses the indoor/outdoor 5G network, a 5G core deployed in the near edge and potentially a 3rd party server brought by the drone operator company to host the drone service.

3.2.2 Measured KPIs

The KPIs that have been examined in this first phase of dry run testing are presented in Table 2.

⁵ <https://www.gateworks.com>

Table 2: Measured KPIs (i2CAT).

KPIs	Segment	Description	Measuring process
Network throughput	Conn	Obtain measurements of the communication link bandwidth (in Mbps).	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 3
Network latency	Conn	Measure network latency by pinging different points of the infrastructure (in sec).	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 3
Jitter	Conn	Measure the variation in the delay of received packets (in sec).	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 3
Resource Utilization	Comp	Monitor CPU and RAM usage of the processing devices.	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 3

3.2.3 Description of Tested Cases

The tests performed in the i2CAT laboratory focus on isolated performance evaluations of the three segments considered by the KFT: the radio access network, the transport network, and the computing segment. We define a set of dedicated scenarios for the different technologies and present the corresponding results.

3.2.3.1 Scenario A: Private Wi-Fi network evaluations

Scenario A, presented in Table 3, evaluates the isolated performance of private Wi-Fi network communications, in particular a Wi-Fi5 (IEEE 802.11ac) based access point to which an end device connects. The chosen hardware for this experiment is an OpenWifi element from Edgecore and a Gateworks single board computer (SBC) as user equipment.

Table 3: Scenario A description (i2CAT).

Test Case (TC) Setup: The setup will consist of one Edgecore (Openwifi) ECW5211-L acting as a Wi-Fi access point and one Gateworks (armhf based SBC) which will connect to this access point. The Gateworks will be equipped with a miniPCIe ath10k based Wireless Network Interface Card (NIC) that will allow the SBC to connect to the Wi-Fi access point that the Edgecore device will have deployed.

- End devices:
 - Edgecore ECW5211-L
 - Gateworks SBC
- Access devices:

The access point will be configured on the 5 GHz spectrum using an 80 MHz bandwidth. Both the Edgecore and the Gateworks' Network Interface Cards support IEEE 802.11ac capabilities.

 - Edgecore access point radiating on the 5GHz band, supports 802.11ac.
 - Gateworks SBC: Wi-Fi client that will connect to the 5GHz access point mentioned above, supports 802.11ac as well.

Tools Used: iperf3, ping

Metering Process: An iperf3 server will be instantiated on the Edgecore access point; the Gateworks SBC will then start a client session to this server. In order to obtain downlink results iperf3 offers a "reverse" option on

which the server will be responsible to send data to the client. The KPI will be retrieved always on the receiving end of the iperf3 connection.

Prerequisites	Operational access Wi-Fi network (access point) and compatible UE.		
Necessary test data	None		
Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Deploy the access point on the Edgecore.	An access point on the 5GHz band has been deployed.
	Step 2	Connect the Gateworks SBC to the access point.	The Gateworks SBC is connected to the access point.
	Step 3	Start an iperf3 server on the Edgecore.	An iperf3 server is now waiting for connections.
	Step 5	Start the iperf3 experiments on the Gateworks SBC.	Successfully execution of downlink and uplink iperf3 experiments.
	Step 4	Perform a ping test.	Ping test is performed successfully.
	Step 5	Retrieval of KPIs.	KPIs successfully retrieved from both the Edgecore and the Gateworks SBC.
Test Case comments:	None		

3.2.3.1.1 Measurement results

3.2.3.1.1.1 Network throughput & latency

Network latency

In these experiments the goal is to measure how responsive the Wi-Fi network is, i.e., how fast it reacts to a request. To calculate the latency (round-trip time-RTT), we used the ping tool, where a request and reply packet are transmitted. The experiments are performed in both directions (uplink and downlink), using either the Wi-Fi client (uplink) or the Wi-Fi access point (downlink) as origin of the ping. Figure 3 shows an exemplary series of captures of 120 s taken during an experiment repetition.

Figure 3: Wi-Fi two-way latency experiment results (i2CAT).

We measure an average delay of 4.88 ms when initiating the ping in the Wi-Fi client and 5.3 ms, when initiating the ping in the access point. The jitter is relatively small, as can be seen, moving in the range from 4.4 ms to 6.6 ms, the higher values being outliers. The performance in both directions is well in the range of typical Wi-Fi communications. Note that the one-way delay is half of the values presented in this section.

Network throughput

During the iperf3-based tests, the private Wi-Fi network capacity (throughput) is tested. Since protocols and traffic direction are parameters that affect the total throughput of the network, four different scenarios are detected and tested to obtain reliable and contrasted data: UDP and TCP traffic, in uplink and downlink, respectively.

a) TCP Throughput

These two experiments show the performance of iperf3 using the TCP transport protocol. This protocol will actively negotiate a stable data rate approaching the actual capacity of the link, thus giving us a clear example of the amount of data transfer that the network can reliably handle at a time. A 40 s samples of the throughput during TCP-based test of the private Wi-Fi network are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Wi-Fi TCP throughput; uplink & downlink experiments (i2CAT).

We observe the following key performance values:

TCP Downlink (DL):

- Average: 390.68 Mbps
- Standard Deviation: 10.09 Mbps

TCP Uplink (UL):

- Average: 230.71 Mbps
- Standard Deviation: 1.63 Mbps

The performance in both directions surpasses the basic requirements of standard media services, e.g., a 4K video streaming and the performance is stable (with slightly more variations in the downlink, that, however, features much high downlink capacity).

b) UDP Throughput

This protocol does not implement any reliability (no acknowledgements are sent when data packets are received). As such, it can be used to inject as much traffic as possible, driving the network to saturation and it is usually used to benchmark the network's maximum throughput and for services that require high data transfer rate. The typical behaviour can be seen in the 40 s sample shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Wi-Fi UDP throughput; uplink & downlink experiments (i2CAT).

We observe the following key performance values:

UDP DL:

- Average: 430.93 Mbps
- Standard Deviation: 8.27 Mbps

UDP UL:

- Average: 240.1 Mbps
- Standard Deviation: 18.75 Mbps

The peak throughput in both directions with UDP surpasses the one with TCP due to the nature of the saturating UDP traffic. Yet the ranges are very similar.

3.2.3.2 Scenario B: Private 5G network evaluations

Scenario B, presented in Table 4, evaluates the isolated performance of 5G standalone cellular communications in a private network composed of an Amarisoft Callbox and an Amarisoft network core that is embedded within the solution. The tests are executed in the i2CAT laboratory environment, using the band n77 and 40 MHz of spectrum. The setup also includes a Quectel modem that can be connected to a laptop as a UE.

Table 4: Scenario B description (i2CAT).

TC Setup: A 5G network is deployed using an Amarisoft CallBox Pro and its embedded Amarisoft Core, then a Quectel UE will connect to this network and perform throughput and latency tests. The network is deployed in the band n77 spectrum.

- End devices:
 - Amarisoft CallBox Pro
 - Quectel UE
- Access Devices:
 - 1 Amarisoft 5G base station (BS), band 77, 4x4 MIMO
 - 1 UE Quectel on a mounting kit, supports 4x4 MIMO

Tools Used: iperf3, ping

Metering Process: An iperf3 server is instantiated on the Amarisoft CallBox; the Quectel then starts a client session to the server. In order to obtain downlink results iperf3 offers a ‘reverse’ option on which the server will be responsible to send data to the client. The KPI will be retrieved always on the receiving end of the iperf3 connection.

Prerequisites	Operational access 5G network, operational 5G core.
Necessary test data	None

Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Deploy and configure the 5G network.	The Amarisoft starts radiating on band 77.
	Step 2	Add the UE on the core subscriber list.	The UE can now connect to the network.
	Step 3	Establish a connection to the 5G network.	The UE is now connected to the 5G network.
	Step 5	Start an iperf3 server on the Amarisoft.	An iperf3 server is now waiting for connections.
	Step 4	Start the iperf3 experiments on the Quectel.	Successfully execution of downlink and uplink iperf3 experiments.
	Step 5	Perform a ping test.	Ping test is performed successfully.
	Step 6	Retrieval of KPIs.	KPIs successfully retrieved from both the Amarisoft and the Quectel.

Test Case comments: None

3.2.3.2.1 Measurement results

The following data is retrieved using an Amarisoft CallBox Pro to deploy a 5G network with the settings mentioned on the Table 5 and a Quectel RM500Q-L acting as UE on i2CAT’s laboratory. Similar to the Wi-Fi experiments, a set of iperf3 and ping experiments are performed to evaluate the latency and bandwidth of the 5G network.

3.2.3.2.1.1 Network throughput & latency

Network latency

In Figure 6, the distribution of timings (RTT) for the ping experiments can be seen; the average RTT for both directions is 18.94 ms which means that the one-way latency is around 9.5 ms. We observe an average jitter of 5.76 ms of the RTT. For the calculation of the jitter, we use the standard deviation calculated from the measured time series.

Figure 6: Histogram of the RTT measured with the private 5G network (i2CAT).

Network throughput

We employed iperf3 for our tests due to its widespread adoption in network performance evaluations. Figure 7 shows the typical observed throughput during evaluations for the 4 configurations adopted in the experiments (TCP/UDP UL and DL).

Figure 7: Throughput results for the private 5G network with UDP and TCP in UL and DL (i2CAT).

The following performance is measured overall:

TCP DL:

- Average: 186.27 Mbps
- Standard Deviation: 15.41 Mbps

TCP UL:

- Average: 40.35 Mbps
- Standard Deviation: 3.69 Mbps

UDP DL:

- Average: 209.23 Mbps
- Standard Deviation: 13.7 Mbps

UDP UL:

- Average: 39.07 Mbps
- Standard Deviation: 1.21 Mbps

It is noteworthy to highlight that the total throughput achieved with the 5G network is below the performance of for example a Wi-Fi network, as described in the previous section. This can be explained by the fact that only half the bandwidth is used (here 40 MHz), given the limitations with the usage of the private spectrum in Spain. Also, it should be pointed out, that there is a strong asymmetry between the upload and download throughput. The default configuration used for these experiments, a configuration applied in many cellular networks, assigns more resources to the downlink (so that users can consume content, like online videos). Independently from these two observations, the achieved throughput seems to deliver a sufficiently stable and powerful performance to host a variety of services, even demanding ones, like 4K video transmissions.

3.2.3.3 Scenario C: Public 4G/5G network evaluations

Scenario C, presented in Table 5, focuses on the evaluation of KPIs for rural cellular networks. In particular, the public 4G and 5G networks are available in the region in which the i2CAT testbed is deployed (in and around Mora la Nova, Tarragona, Spain). The measurements are performed by connecting a smartphone with different SIM cards (one for 4G, one for 5G) to the public networks and executing performance measurements, while at the same time identifying the main characteristics of the cellular network the smartphones are connected to (such as signal strength to the base station). A total of 23 locations are used for these evaluations that are performed jointly with the TDA 5G Rural project⁶.

Table 5: Scenario C description (i2CAT).

TC Setup:

A 4G+5G-capable Smartphone with dual SIM (one for 4G networks, one for 5G) is used. The user carries the smartphone to different locations and performs measurements with public cellular networks.

- End Devices:
 - 1 Smartphone

Tools Used: Ookla speed test (measures throughput and ping), net stat tool to gather information on the radio characteristics.

Metering Process: At each predetermined measurement location, the net stat tool is used to capture relevant information on the connection quality towards the 4G/5G networks. Then the speed test is launched, and the results are stored.

Prerequisites	Moving to the measurement location, smartphone equipped with 4G and 5G-compatible SIM cards, public cellular network coverage
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⁶ <https://i2cat.net/tda-5g-rural/>

Necessary test data	None		
Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Activate 4G or 5G SIM.	Connection to cellular network is established.
	Step 2	Measure radio channel metrics with net stat tool.	Information on the key parameters of the connections can be captured.
	Step 3	Capture current location with GPS.	Location details are captured to later associate measurements to a specific place.
	Step 5	Launch speedtest.	The Ookla speed test is executed and download and upload measurements are performed, yielding throughputs per location.

Test Case comments:
 The 23 visited locations are chosen to be either points of interest, such as gasoline stations, or public buildings. Due to the lacking 5G coverage in rural areas, some locations did not yield very good or even no 5G results, due to bad or missing connectivity.

Figure 8: Map of public 4G/5G measurement locations close to Mora d'Ebre (i2CAT).

3.2.3.3.1 Measurement results

In the following, we present the main outcomes of the public cellular network measurement campaign. The map shown in Figure 8 marks the location in the region in and around Mora d'Ebre in which measurements have been performed.

The performance measured at the 23 locations (some are overlapping in the map view), is shown in Figure 9, whereas the measured pings (RTT) are shown Figure 10.

Figure 9: Throughput measurement results for public 4G/5G networks (i2CAT).

Figure 10: Ping measurements results for public 4G/5G networks (i2CAT).

3.2.3.3.1.1 Network throughput & latency

We observe the following results with 4G network connectivity:

- DL Speed: The average speed is 78.80 Mbps with a maximum of 149.00 Mbps and a minimum of 15.00 Mbps.

- **UL Speed:** The average speed is 26.61 Mbps with a maximum of 81.00 Mbps and a minimum of 2.50 Mbps.
- **Latency:** The average response time is 37.65 ms, with a maximum of 84.00 ms and a minimum of 21.00 ms.

We observe the following results with 5G network connectivity:

- **DL Speed:** The average speed is 33.48 Mbps with a maximum of 83.00 Mbps and a minimum of 4 Mbps. It was observed that there is at least one location without 5G connection.
- **UL Speed:** The average speed is 16.00 Mbps with a maximum of 48.00 Mbps and a minimum of 2 Mbps.
- **Latency:** The average response time is 40.30 ms, with a maximum of 80.00 ms and a minimum of 35.5 ms.

The 4G measurements show higher download and upload speeds compared to the 5G measurements. This can be explained by the fact that 4G coverage is much broader in the territory and that 4G can benefit from carrier aggregation that combines different bands to improve performance. The latency for 5G (Vodafone) is slightly higher on average compared to 4G (Movistar), although the difference is not large. It should also be noted that there are locations in the 5G (Vodafone) data where measurements are zero, suggesting a lack of network connection or a problem with the measurement.

Based on the analysed data, it can be observed that Movistar's 4G measurements are generally better in terms of download speed, upload speed, and latency compared to Vodafone's 5G measurements. It should be taken into account that there are locations where Vodafone 5G does not provide a connection, which can affect overall statistics. This observation can be extrapolated to other rural regions, where 5G availability may be limited and while it may perform very well near base stations, away from them coverage may be fragile and result in performance inferior to 4G.

Overall, it can be stated that some services and applications could use the public network, however, the performance is not stable enough for high requirement services or services that require an edge computation to host services, which is not available in public networks.

3.2.3.4 Scenario D: mmWave transport link evaluations

Scenario D, presented in Table 6, focuses on the evaluation of medium-long range mmWave transport links. As described in Section 3.2.1, the i2CAT infrastructure features a total of three radio transport links: the 80 and 70 GHz PtP and the 60 GHz PtMP link. Note that the latter is just used for this test in PtP mode, i.e., there is no third element connected to the 60 GHz network.

Table 6: Scenario D description (i2CAT).

TC Setup:

- **Transport devices**
 - The Siklu devices (60 GHz PtMP, 70 + 80 GHz PtP) act as source and destination for traffic.
 - Links are established between each pair of Siklu mmWave devices.
 - The 80 GHz link covers a distance of 3.5 km, whereas the 60 and 70 GHz links cover around 300m.
 - Dedicated (fibre-based) access to the transport devices allows for management and configuration.

Tools Used: iperf3, ping

Metering Process: iperf3 and ping are part of the toolset made available by Siklu and run on their devices on-demand for testing sessions. Metrics about the link (signal quality, modulation coding scheme, etc.) are being collected also automatically during operation.

Prerequisites Operational Siklu links (power and alignment of devices needed)

Necessary test data Iperf3 (UDP/TCP) data transmission is generated automatically by the tools used

Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Establish connection of transport links.	Connection is established.
	Step 2	Log remotely into Siklu devices.	Access is granted and terminal/dashboard is accessible.
	Step 3	Initialize iperf3 from one endpoint of the link to the other.	Data transmission is started.
	Step 4	Verify that data is received on the other endpoint.	Received data rate is measured.
	Step 5	UDP and TCP streams are tested. KPI extraction.	UDP/TCP results are captured.
	Step 6	Direction of transmission is inverted to test link in the other direction, Steps 3-5 are repeated. KPI extraction.	Results for inverted direction are obtained.
	Step 7	Ping is started from one end to another. KPI extraction.	Ping measurements are captured.

Test Case comments: None

3.2.3.4.1 Measurement results

3.2.3.4.1.1 Network throughput & latency

From the measurements performed, we obtain a series of insights that allow us to understand the capacity and stability/reliability of the transport solution based on mmWave links. It is important to highlight, that for the evaluations performed we are bound to the existing setup and cannot move the endpoints of the links. This is important to mention, since the link quality observed for each of the links might not always be the optimal one and it may vary depending on the weather conditions. For the testing, we selected a sunny day with no special weather conditions and performed the repetitions.

Network throughput

We evaluate the three link types separately (70 and 80 GHz PtP, 60 GHz PtMP). In Table 7 we show the three devices, the estimated throughput (which is a value produced by the devices, based on the observed link quality) and the measured throughput. First, we observe that only the 60 GHz PtMP link has a good enough signal to provide close to the expected throughput of the link: its nominal performance is 1 Gbps and it reaches around 740 Mbps with the highest modulation coding scheme. The estimated throughput is provided by the dashboard of the devices and calculated by the devices itself. The deviation observed in the 80 GHz link is important, and it

can be affected either if non-optimal channel conditions are present (e.g., due to specific weather conditions like rain or fog) or if there is a misalignment of the end devices that yields inferior connection quality.

Table 7: Scenario D throughput evaluation (i2CAT).

Link Type	Distance	Nominal Capacity (Mbps)	Estimated Throughput (Mbps)	Measured Throughput (Mbps)	Measured standard deviation (Mbps)
80 GHz PtP	3.5 Km	10000	6400	4384.19	43.33
70 GHz PtP	300 m	1000	350	149.35	3.81
60 GHz PtMP	300 m	1000	1000	738.83	23.68

Network latency

We continue the evaluations by looking at the round-trip time in Table 8. The latency in all three links is very low and stable. While not reaching the same latency as a fibre or ethernet-based connection, the wireless links show a very high performance under favourable weather conditions (no rain, snow or fog). Together with the throughput results and combining the information with the weather data available from an on-site weather station, we conclude that the weather conditions do not impact the measurements performed in the test scenario. The 60 GHz link performs very well, and we note that both the 80 and the 70 GHz link are underperforming (the 70 GHz noticeably, probably due to suboptimal alignment of the two endpoints). This cause will be further investigated. One issue that could be impacting the 80 GHz link performance is the fact that the link spans over a river.

Table 8: Scenario D latency evaluation (i2CAT).

Link Type	RTT (ms)	Standard Deviation (ms)
80 GHz PtP	0.457	0.07
70 GHz PtP	1.370	0.191
60 GHz PtmP	0.651	0.049

3.2.3.5 Scenario E: Raspberry Pi 4 evaluation

Scenario E, presented in

Table 9, evaluates Raspberry Pi 4 devices while implementing the far edge computing layer. Raspberry Pi devices are known for being small yet powerful, making them great for these close-up scenarios. Our tests are designed to determine the strengths and potential limitations of these devices. The expected result of such a comparative analysis is to help characterise and measure the far edge layer in terms of computational capabilities, network latency, and data throughput. Furthermore, this benchmarking aids in identifying potential bottlenecks, ensuring optimised resource allocation, and guiding infrastructural decisions to enhance overall system performance.

Table 9: Scenario E description (i2CAT).

TC Setup: A benchmarking server (Intel NUC11PAHi5 Barebone i5-1135G7) will run the necessary scripts to benchmark the devices. The testbed is composed by 3x Raspberry Pi 4. The devices will be representing the far edge computing layer.

- Computation devices
 - Intel NUC:

- Type: Intel NUC11PAHi5 Barebone i5-1135G7, 2.4-4.2 GHz
- CPU: 4 cores. 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-1135G7 @ 2.40GHz
- RAM: 16GB
- Disk: SSD 500GB

Tools Used: iperf3, ping, stress, vmstat and python scripts which automate the benchmarking process, running the different tests and storing the results in different files.

Metering Process: In our dynamic testing setup, a benchmarking server is deployed which basically runs python scripts that perform the measurement of different computing KPIs. To do so, it attacks the devices that represent the far edge layer. We will evaluate KPIs individually to ensure there's no concurrent behavioural interference.

Prerequisites Operational computing devices forming the far edge layer, with internet connectivity and interconnection between them.

Necessary test data None

	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
Activity	Step 1	Preparation of the testbed. Devices are mounting.	Operational far edge testbed.
	Step 2	Preparation of the benchmarking server.	Operational benchmarking server.
	Step 3	Installation of the dependencies for the python scripts. Installation of measuring tools on the target devices.	Benchmarking ready to be performed.
	Step 4	Benchmarking execution.	KPIs extraction.

Test Case comments: None

3.2.3.5.1 Measurement results

Scenario E tackles the computing segment of the network. The devices have been benchmarked using typical compute related KPIs such as network latency, network throughput and resource utilisation. The idea behind this scenario is to tangibly measure how far edge type devices behave.

The theory states that the closer the computing layer is located to the data source generation, the quicker the processing will be handled, arriving then to the classical trade-off between processing time, processing capabilities and available physical space where the computing node could be placed. Besides, usually layers close to the user such as the far edge, have more stringent requirements in terms of available physical space than layers such as near edge or cloud. Due to this, the computing candidate spectrum gets reduced to smaller (and generally) less-powerful devices, which could satisfy such a requirement, like Raspberry Pi devices.

3.2.3.5.1.1 Network throughput & latency

Network latency

Studying network latency in the Raspberry Pi (representing far edge layer) is vital to assess its suitability for latency-sensitive applications. Lower latency devices closer to end-users ensure better user experiences, efficient data processing, and optimal bandwidth usage. To do so, and as previously done for other scenarios, network

latency has been measured through the ping tool. Figure 11 illustrates that devices located at the far edge exhibit latency measurements approximately 0.4 ms. This indicates minimal incremental latency associated with employing this computational layer in close proximity to where packets are generated. The jitter varies approximately from 0.19 ms to 0.75 ms across the 3 devices, probably caused by a higher congestion in the network switches of the network fabric that interconnects the setup in the i2CAT lab.

Figure 11: Network latency measurements for far edge layer (i2CAT).

Network throughput

In assessing network throughput,

Figure 12 showcases data transfer rates across the far edge layer using iperf3 as a benchmark. Devices consistently demonstrate high throughput values, near to 900 Mbps, which satisfy the requirements of a standard media streaming app (e.g., a 4K video streaming). The observed consistency across the spectrum is bounded by the peak capacity of the switches and links, that interconnect these devices.

Figure 12: Network throughput measurements for far edge layer (i2CAT).

3.2.3.5.1.2 Resource utilisation

Table 10: Scenario E far edge characteristics (i2CAT).

Layer	CPU	RAM
Far edge	4 cores. Broadcom BCM2711, Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.8GHz	8GB

In Table 10 we present the characteristics of the Raspberry Pi 4, devices selected for implementing the far edge layer.

a) CPU Utilisation

To ensure a fair comparison between the different devices forming the testbed, the same computational load is applied to the devices. Specifically, a mathematical calculation involving the Fibonacci sequence is executed on all devices to assess CPU consumption.

The far edge layer consistently shows a higher CPU utilisation for user processes, leaving it nearly exhausted with minimal idle time. On its own, Figure 13 may not provide substantial insights. However, when juxtaposed with scenario F, where the same study is conducted selecting different devices that are usually used for implementing the near edge layer, it offers valuable data to assess CPU performance.

Figure 13: CPU measurements for far edge layer (i2CAT).

b) RAM Utilisation

To ensure a consistent assessment of memory usage across various devices, we employ the same method for data structure creation on each device. As shown in Figure 14, the far edge devices have a fairly consistent high RAM utilization, with an average used RAM of around 52%. Similar to the CPU analysis, these results in isolation do not provide significant insights. Yet, they gain value in relation to the findings from scenario F.

Figure 14: RAM measurements for far edge layer (i2CAT).

3.2.3.6 Scenario F: NUC compute evaluations

Shifting towards computing layers that necessitate greater processing prowess, the near edge is often best served by devices like-NUCs. The NUC's appeal lies in its robust computing capabilities which it seamlessly blends with a compact form factor. The combination of robust computing capabilities and a compact form factor makes the NUC an optimal choice for more computing demanding edge applications. Whether it is handling more complex computational tasks or dealing with larger data sets, the NUC stands out as a competent and efficient solution in the near edge of computing continuum. Through our tests, we aim to learn about the NUC's capabilities, how well they connect to networks, and their processing strengths and weaknesses. The expected result is to measure the near edge layer in terms of computational capabilities, network latency, and data throughput. Furthermore, this benchmarking aids in identifying potential bottlenecks, ensuring optimised resource allocation, and guiding infrastructural decisions to enhance overall system performance. The behaviour of NUCs is investigated in Scenario F, which is presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Scenario F description (i2CAT).

TC Setup: A benchmarking server (Intel NUC11PAHi5 Barebone i5-1135G7) will run the necessary scripts to benchmark the near edge type computing layer devices. The testbed is composed by 3x Intel NUCs which represent the near edge computing layer.

- Computation devices
 - Intel NUC:
 - Type: Intel NUC11PAHi5 Barebone i5-1135G7, 2.4-4.2 GHz
 - CPU: 4 cores. 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-1135G7 @ 2.40GHz
 - RAM: 16GB
 - Disk: SSD 500GB

Tools Used: iperf3, ping, stress, vmstat and python scripts which automate the benchmarking process, running the different tests and storing the results in different files.

Metering Process: In our dynamic testing setup, a benchmarking server is deployed which runs python scripts that perform the measurement of different computing KPIs. To do so, it attacks the devices that represent the near edge layer. We will evaluate KPIs individually to ensure there is no concurrent behavioural interference.

Prerequisites	Operational computing devices forming the near edge layer, with internet connectivity and interconnection between them.		
Necessary test data	None.		
Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Preparation of the testbed. Devices are mounting.	Operational near edge testbed.
	Step 2	Preparation of the benchmarking server.	Operational benchmarking server.
	Step 3	Installation of the dependencies for the python scripts. Installation of measuring tools on the target devices.	Benchmarking ready to be performed.
	Step 4	Benchmarking execution. KPI extraction	Results for throughput, ping and CPU/RAM utilization captured.

Test Case comments: None

3.2.3.6.1 Measurement results

3.2.3.6.1.1 Network throughput & latency

Before analysing the network latency results, it is worth mentioning that in our implementation we try to implement a greater physical/virtual separation between edge layers, respecting that the far edge (analysed in Scenario E) should sit closer to the generation of the data (which in these scenarios is the benchmarking server) than the near edge. Since in this round of dry-run test for the computing segment we are hosting the devices in the same location (i2CAT lab), the only way to increase the separation of the devices (emulating a greater separation of near edge devices with respect far edge devices) was to place an additional switch between the benchmarking server and the near edge devices.

Network latency

From Figure 15 it is observable that latency values are less than 1ms. As previously stated, these values highly depend on the separation between the data generation (in our case the benchmarking server) and the NUCs. A slight jitter could be noticed, varying from 0.21 ms to 1.1 ms probably caused by a higher congestion in the network fabric as it happened in Scenario E.

Figure 15: Network latency measurements for near edge layer (i2CAT).

Network throughput

In assessing network throughput, Figure 16 consistently demonstrate high throughput values, nearing 900 Mbps, results very similar to those of the Raspberry Pis in the E scenario. Such results, as previously mentioned, are bounded by the peak capacity of the switches and links, that interconnect these devices.

Figure 16: Network throughput measurements for near edge layer (i2CAT).

3.2.3.6.1.2 Resource utilisation

Table 12: Scenario F near edge characteristics (i2CAT).

Layer	CPU	RAM
Near edge	4 cores. 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-1135G7 @ 2.40GHz	16GB

In Table 12 we present the characteristics of the NUCs, devices used for implementing the near edge layer.

a) CPU Utilization

Figures 17 reflects a lower percentage of CPU usage that the one compared in scenario E. While user processes in the far edge layer occupy a dominant percentage of CPU, the near edge layer only utilizes roughly 60% for user processes, offering significantly more idle CPU time. This indicates that the near edge layer has more available computational capacity when handling the same RAM processes as the far edge layer.

Figure 17: CPU measurements for near edge layer (i2CAT).

b) RAM Utilisation

As performed in Scenario E, to maintain a consistent evaluation of memory usage across different devices, we implement uniform data structures using a consistent approach on each device. Figure 18 shows an average used RAM of around 20%.

Figure 18: RAM measurements for near edge layer (i2CAT).

3.3 UC Conclusions

Since the final pilot testbed is not yet fully usable, as parts of the infrastructure are still deployed in the Barcelona laboratory environment, a mixture of on-site tests and inhouse tests is performed. In the access segment, Wi-Fi, 4G and 5G (both public and private) are tested. We observe that a private Wi-Fi network can achieve high throughput between 200 and around 400 Mbps in the download and around 200 Mbps in the upload with very small latency of around 5 ms. It is important to note that this performance is for single device tests, and results might change substantially with more devices, since they compete for the available radio resources.

In the measurements done in public locations of the area around Mora la Nova, we observe that there is a decent 4G coverage that yields a varying performance depending on how close a base station is. Thanks to carrier aggregation, sometimes download speeds of over 100 Mbps can be achieved, with an average of around 79 Mbps. The upload, however, is limited and only reaches an average of 27 Mbps. This is due to the asymmetry of cellular networks, that normally always give priority to the downstream traffic. The average delay is of around 38 ms.

When testing 5G networks in the area, we realise that the coverage is poor and some of the locations do not feature 5G at all. Also, the deployed 5G networks are very sparse and unless we measure close to a BS, the performance is subpar. As such, we only observe 33 Mbps of download and 16 Mbps of upload capacity and an average latency of 40 ms. The need to close the digital gap and provide better 5G network coverage becomes evident when looking at these results. When switching to a private 5G standalone network, the performance clearly improves: around 190 Mbps of download and 40 Mbps of upload capacity, as well as RTT latencies of around 19 ms are enough to serve a variety of services with significant requirements.

The transport network evaluations show that it is key for the alignment to be optimal when using mmWave transport links. We observe this especially in the 70 GHz PtP link. In the long-range 80 GHz PtP link we can assume a good alignment, but still, the expected 10 Gbps cannot be achieved. This could be due to the mixed topology between the two points that are connected, which include a river and a metal bridge. Still, the capacity is enough to satisfy the transport of up to 3-4 Gbps of data in both directions.

When evaluating the computing devices available in the laboratory, we look at their standalone performance, but also the impact the different edge layers have on the performance. In our analysis, the far edge layer (Raspberry Pi devices) consistently demonstrates lower network latency than the near edge (NUC devices), aligning with theoretical expectations. Both the far edge and near edge layers exhibit similar network throughput results, primarily constrained by the network fabric interconnecting the testbed. As for resource utilisation, while the far edge layer's CPU is nearly exhausted with user processes, the near edge layer, for the same workload, only utilises roughly 60% for user processes. This suggests a more efficient computational resource handling in the near edge. Furthermore, the near edge layer displayed roughly 1.7 times more idle RAM than the far edge layer, indicating a greater memory availability in the near edge layer when processing the same data structure.

Finally, additional testing iterations will be executed in the next phase where the E2E integrated scenarios will be investigated that combine access, transport and computing technologies.

4 UC 2: e-Health (Greece)

4.1 Overview of the Service Supported by UC

E-Health applications are growing rapidly and are often seen as a potential way to reduce health care costs, especially for older people. CAPTAIN COACH provides artificial intelligence (AI) services such as movement, and speech analysis to enhance wellbeing in older adults' everyday life targeting to recommendations and interventions about cognitive, physical, social, and nutritional aspects. Specifically considering, usual cases for rural environment, that the older adults may live in villages in remote areas there is the need for good network connectivity and accurate results in terms of AI mechanisms to be better served. Consequently, the examination of various connectivity technologies and different processing devices for the execution of AI services, related to elderly monitoring, is of utmost importance.

In UC2 pilot (WP5), led by CAPTAIN, high data rate connectivity solutions for older people will be examined. Nonetheless, due to the requirement for 5G spectrum allocation from regulatory authorities, including a mobile network operator, which falls outside the XGain's scope, conducting the connectivity testing with ICCS laboratory infrastructure in the pilot site (Central Macedonia) is unfeasible. In current dry-run testing phase, connectivity and computation measurements are presented in ICCS laboratory, where there is access to 5G spectrum through approval from the Hellenic Telecommunications & Post Commission.

4.2 Lab Testing Framework

4.2.1 Testing Scenarios

In time writing the content for Deliverable D3.3, the final integrated representative testing scenarios have not been determined yet, however there is a clear view about the concepts. The general idea for the laboratory infrastructure, shown also in Figure 19, is the appropriate integration of different connectivity (ICCS and ICOM) and processing devices (CAPTAIN BOX, called also as BOX, and ICCS's devices) to test the performance of these configurations under different AI services that are related with remote elderly monitoring. Under this framework, we provide the ability for services' execution to be done closer to the source of data in edge-cloud continuum and create a compute continuum topology that captures different edge levels including extreme, far and near layers. Allocation of processing devices in different layers of compute continuum combines the better processing capacity towards the cloud with the lower communication latency towards the edge. Thus, in Figure 19 we have identified a few possible deployment options in the compute continuum that we will investigate based on the criteria of network, and case study requirements. In next phase of Task 3.4, it will be studied if a better performance can be achieved by ICCS devices, subject to network and computation (considering both the resources' utilization and the inference latency of AI services) related metrics, compared with the BOX.

To make the integration and testing of compute continuum in next step of Task 3.4, isolated measurements from the potential pool of technologies that are possible to be used are provided in the current deliverable. Specifically, in terms of connectivity ICCS tests its 5G RAN infrastructure, while ICOM provides measurements for its WiBAS™ PtMP and UltraLink™ PtP links. The latter technologies are able to be applied as transport links connecting ICCS gNB to the core, across the points A and B, as shown in Figure 19. Additionally, for the computation segment, CAPTAIN provides measurements about the BOX functionality and ICCS tests the performance of an NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin based on detection of pose of a person and speech to text generation, services offered by CAPTAIN. The measurements in the following description have been made based on the equipment below:

ICCS Testbed

- Connectivity segment:
 - gNB USRP N310
 - NR band: N78 @3.4Ghz
 - 5G stack: OpenAirInterface (OAI) RAN, OAI Core
 - UE: Teltonica RUTX50 industrial 5G router
- Computation segment:
 - NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin
 - GPU: NVIDIA Ampere architecture with 2048 NVIDIA CUDA cores and 64 Tensor cores
 - CPU: 12-core Arm Cortex-A78AE v8.2 64-bit
 - RAM: 32GB 256-bit LPDDR5

ICOM Testbed

- Connectivity segment:
 - WiBAS™ G5 BS and 2 G5 terminal stations, operating at 24.25-29.50 GHz
 - UltraLink™-GX80 consisting of two side-nodes, operating at 71-76/81-86 GHz.

CAPTAIN BOX

- Computation segment:
 - Raspberry Pi 4 Model B
 - CPU: 4 cores. Broadcom BCM2711, Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.8GHz
 - RAM: 8GB
 - Disk: MicroSD 64GB Class 10 U3 V30 A1 UHS-I
- Micro-projector DLP® LightCrafter Display 2000 Evaluation Module (EVM)
- Soundspeaker Xiaomi Mi Pocket 2

Figure 19: E2E laboratory infrastructure (ICCS).

4.2.2 Measured KPIs

The KPIs that have been examined in this first phase of dry run testing are presented in

Table 13, Table 14 and Table 15.

Table 13: Measured KPIs (ICCS).

KPIs	Segment	Description	Measuring process
Network throughput	Conn	Obtain measurements of the communication link bandwidth (in Mbps).	Number of executions: 2 Duration: 3 min
Network latency	Conn	Measure network latency by pinging different points of the infrastructure (in sec).	Number of executions: 3 Duration: 3 min
Jitter	Conn	Measure the variation in the delay of received packets (in sec).	Number of executions: 3 Duration: 3 min
Resource utilisation	Comp	Monitor CPU, GPU and RAM usage of the Jetson device.	Number of executions per service: 1 Duration (Video): 8.5 min Audio samples: 648
Processing latency	Comp	Time between request generated, and service response received (in sec).	Number of executions per service: 1 Duration (Video): 8.5 min Audio samples: 648

Table 14: Measured KPIs (ICOM).

KPIs	Segment	Description	Measuring process
Network throughput	Conn	Obtain measurements of the communication link bandwidth (in Mbps).	Number of executions: 3 Duration: 1 min
Network latency	Conn	Measure network latency by pinging different points of the infrastructure (in sec).	Number of executions: 3 Duration: 1 min
Jitter	Conn	Measure the variation in the delay of received packets (in sec).	Number of executions: 3 Duration: 1 min

Table 15: Measured KPIs (CAPT).

KPIs	Segment	Description	Measuring process
Resource utilisation	Comp	Monitor CPU and RAM usage of the Raspberry Pi 4 device.	Number of executions: Running 24h Duration: 10 days (continuous operation)

4.2.3 Description of Tested Cases

The tests are performed in the ICCS, ICOM and CAPTAIN private infrastructures focus on isolated performance evaluations and this equipment will be with the radio access network, transport network, and computing segments for the E2E integration phase. Representative scenarios are defined and the results are presented.

4.2.3.1 Scenario A: Private 5G network evaluations

Scenario A, presented in Table 16, evaluates the performance of 5G ICCS private network over the opensource OpenAirInterface (OAI) platform. The tests are executed in the ICCS laboratory environment, using the band n78 at 3.4GHz. The setup includes Teltonika RUTX50 industrial 5G router that can be connected to a laptop and act as the UE, connected to the 5G base station (gNB) exploiting USRP N310 SDR. The setup exploits OAI RAN and OAI Core for performing our respective experiments.

Table 16: Scenario A description (ICCS).

TC Setup: A gNB based on OAI RAN is exploited for the New Radio (NR) 5G access network connected to the OAI Core of the 5G system. For the user equipment we used Teltonika’s RUTX50 Industrial 5G router connected to the OAI RAN for performing throughput and latency tests at N78 (3.4GHz) frequency band.

- End devices:
 - Teltonika’s RUTX50 Industrial 5G Router
- Access Network:
 - 5G gNB USRP N310

Tools Used: iperf3, ping

Metering Process: We exploit the iperf3 tool for performing network throughput measurements (in uplink and downlink direction) at the 5G tested based on the OAI software stack. An iperf3 server is instantiated on the OAI Core; the Teltonika UE then starts a client session to the server. The detailed experimentation steps are indicated below.

Prerequisites	Operational access 5G network, operational 5G core.		
Necessary test data	None		
Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Configure and deploy the 5G network.	(i) The ICCS SA Core based on OAI software is deployed. (ii) The gNB is deployed and connects to the OAI Core. (iii) gNB listens for UE connection requests.
	Step 2	Activate 5G UE	The UE connects to the 5G system (5GS)
	Step 3	Start an iperf3 server on the SA OAI Core.	An iperf3 server is now waiting for connections.
	Step 4	Start the iperf3 client on the UE Teltonika RUTX50.	Connect to the iperf3 server and perform uplink and downlink throughput measurements
	Step 5	Perform a ping test.	Latency measurements between client and server are performed

	Step 6	Retrieval of KPIs.	KPIs successfully retrieved for network throughput and latency measurements.
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Test Case comments: None

4.2.3.1.1 Measurement results

4.2.3.1.1.1 Network throughput & latency

Network latency

In Figure 20, the distribution of RTTs for the ping experiments can be seen and the average RTT is about 13.6 ms and the average jitter is about 3 ms. For the calculation of the jitter, we use the standard deviation calculated from the measured time series.

Figure 20: Histogram of the RTT measured with the private 5G network (ICCS).

Network throughput

Using the iperf3 tool in Figure 21 the distribution of TCP/UDP UL and DL throughputs are depicted for 2 executions of 3 minutes. We observe that the DL throughput (about 107/61Mbps for TCP/UDP) is higher than the UL throughput (9.38/9.44 Mbps for TCP/UDP), however our configuration provides a poor performance mainly in UL, and we plan for the next phase of Task 3.4 to enhance our 5G equipment with Amarisoft technology.

Figure 21: Throughput results for the private 5G network with UDP and TCP in UL and DL (ICCS).

4.2.3.2 Scenario B: PtP mmWave transport link evaluations

Scenario B, presented in Table 17, focuses on the evaluation of long range mmWave transport links. The testing setup comprises of an UltraLink™-GX80 link consisting of two side-nodes, operating at 71-76/81-86 GHz and connected via a lab kit, which incorporates waveguides and attenuators. The laboratory setup is showcased in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Testbed of PtP systems (ICOM).

Table 17: Scenario B description (ICOM).

TC Setup:

- Transport devices
 - The UltraLink™-GX80 devices act as source and destination for traffic
 - Links are established between each pair of UltraLink™-GX80 mmWave devices.
 - The links are connected back-to-back via a lab kit (waveguides and attenuators).
 - Dedicated access to the transport devices allows for management and configuration

Tools Used: iperf3, ping

Metering Process: Linux servers are attached to the ethernet ports of UltraLink™-GX80 systems

Prerequisites Two UltraLink™-GX80 systems.

Necessary test data None

Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Establish connection of transport/backhaul links.	Connection is established.
	Step 2	Log remotely into UltraLink™-GX80 devices.	Access is granted and terminal/dashboard is accessible.
	Step 3	Initialize iperf3 from one endpoint of the link to the other.	Data transmission is started.
	Step 4	Verify that data is received on the other endpoint.	Received data rate is measured.
	Step 5	UDP and TCP streams are tested.	UDP/TCP results are captured.
	Step 6	Direction of transmission is inverted to test link in the other direction, Steps 3-5 are repeated.	Results for inverted direction are obtained.
	Step 7	Ping is started from one end to another.	Ping measurements are captured.

Test Case comments: None

4.2.3.2.1 Measurement results

4.2.3.2.1.1 Network throughput & latency

Network throughput

In Figure 23 and Figure 24 we see that the measured throughput is approximately 10 Gbps in both directions, since our system operates in full-duplex mode. We conducted these tests three times for 60 s both for a single connection as well as multiple simultaneous ones, in order to achieve more accurate results and average results are shown. It is worth noting that the iperf results exhibit deviations between single or multiple connections, which is a typical behaviour of iperf due to reasons such as parallelism, TCP window size, load balancing, TCP slow start etc.

Figure 23: TCP network throughput for UltraLink™ (ICOM).

Figure 24: UDP network throughput for UltraLink™ (ICOM).

Network Latency

In Figure 25 we see that the measured latency (Round Trip Time – RTT) without traffic is on average 0.27 ms with standard deviation (jitter) 0.005 ms, while the average RTT with traffic is 1.05 ms with standard deviation 0.009 ms. It is also worth mentioning that we conducted the latency tests for 60s and three executions showing average results, so as to match the duration of the throughput tests.

Figure 25: Latency measurements for UltraLink™ (ICOM).

4.2.3.3 Scenario C: PtMP system evaluations (for FWA or transport links)

Scenario C, presented in Table 18, focuses on the evaluation of long range Fixed Wireless Access (FWA) links. The testing setup comprises of one WiBAS™ G5 base station and 2 WiBAS™ G5 terminal stations, operating at 24.25-29.50 GHz and connected via a lab kit, which incorporates waveguides and attenuators. The laboratory setup is showcased in Figure 26, while in Figure 27 and Figure 28 WiBAS™ G5 BS and WiBAS™ G5 terminal stations are presented, respectively.

Figure 26: Testbed of PtMP systems (ICOM).

Figure 27: The WiBAS™ G5 dual-BS hub radio (ICOM).

Figure 28: WiBAS™ G5 GigaConnect with low-profile antenna 30 cm (ICOM).

Table 18: Scenario C description (ICOM).

TC Setup:

- WiBAS™ devices (offering access or transport links)
 - Links are established between one WiBAS™ G5 base station and two WiBAS™ G5 terminal stations.
 - The links are connected back-to-back via a lab kit (waveguides and attenuators).
 - Dedicated access to the WiBAS™ systems allows for management and configuration.

Tools Used: iperf3, ping

Metering Process: Linux servers are attached to the Ethernet ports of WiBAS™ G5 BS and terminal stations.

Prerequisites	One WiBAS™ G5 base station and two WiBAS™ G5 terminal stations.		
Necessary test data	None		
Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Establish connection of communication links.	Connection is established.
	Step 2	Log remotely into WiBAS™ G5 base station and two WiBAS™ G5 terminal stations.	Access is granted and terminal/dashboard is accessible.
	Step 3	Initialize iperf3 from one endpoint of the link to the other.	Data transmission is started.

Step 4	Verify that data is received on the other endpoint.	Received data rate is measured.
Step 5	UDP and TCP streams are tested.	UDP/TCP results are captured
Step 6	Direction of transmission is inverted to test link in the other direction, Steps 3-5 are repeated.	Results for inverted direction are obtained.
Step 7	Throughput and latency tests are conducted.	Measurements are exported from the tester.

Test Case comments: None

4.2.3.3.1 Measurement results

4.2.3.3.1.1 Network throughput & latency

Network Throughput

In Figure 29, Figure 30,

Figure 31 and Figure 32, we observe that the measured throughput is approximately 1000 Mbps in downlink direction and 500 Mbps in uplink direction, since our systems operates in half-duplex mode. We conducted these tests three times for 60 s both for a single connection as well as multiple simultaneous ones, in order to achieve more accurate results.

Figure 29: TCP DL measurements for WiBAS™ (ICOM).

Figure 30: UDP DL measurements for WiBAS™ (ICOM).

Figure 31: TCP UL measurements for WiBAS™ (ICOM).

Figure 32: UDP UL measurements for WiBAS™ (ICOM).

Network Latency

In Figure 33, we see that the latency without traffic is on average 5.3 ms with standard deviation (jitter) 1.19 ms, while the average RTT with traffic is 22.3 ms with standard deviation 1.77 ms. It is also worth mentioning that we conducted the latency tests for three executions and 60 s each, so as to match the duration of the throughput tests and the averaged results are shown.

Figure 33: Latency measurements for WiBAS™ (ICOM).

4.2.3.4 Scenario D: CAPTAIN BOX evaluation

Scenario D, presented in Table 19, intends to monitor the performance of BOX in terms of computation segment. To do that, an in-laboratory test is performed where a user joins some interventions (Quiz, Day Insights, Day

Agenda, Serious Games, Physical Suggestions, Social Recommendations, Nutritional Recommendations, Event Recommendations), of the BOX for total 1 hour per day for 10 days and statistics related to resource utilization are recorded. CAPTAIN BOX authenticates the user after the user enters the camera’s field of view and then CAPTAIN’s AI executes all interventions that Day Agenda scheduled for the days that device is powered on.

Table 19: Scenario D description (CAPT).

TC Setup:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ CAPTAIN BOX • Computation devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Raspberry Pi 4 Model B <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CPU: 4 cores. Broadcom BCM2711, Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.8GHz ▪ RAM: 8GB ▪ Disk: MicroSD 64GB Class 10 U3 V30 A1 UHS-I 			
Tools Used: Glances, an open-source system cross-platform tool			
Metering Process: CAPTAIN BOX is connected via Wi-Fi on a TP-LINK Archer C6 v2 Router with 1Gbps network speed. Within Box, a monitoring tool that monitor the traffic locally is installed.			
Prerequisites	Operational BOX and network		
Necessary test data	None		
Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Powered on CAPTAIN BOX device.	CAPTAIN BOX powered on
	Step 2	Show CAPTAIN’s logo.	CAPTAIN BOX is successfully connected to Wi-Fi.
	Step 3	User stands in front of the camera for authentication.	CAPTAIN’s authentication service successfully identifies person.
	Step 4	Intervention should start for the user.	Micro-projector lights on and shows application to user.
	Step 5	User should hear CAPTAIN’s soundspeaker commands	Completed
	Step 6	User responds with voice to interact	CAPTAIN’s Box receives voice and through Speech-to-Text (STT) processes the command
	Step 7	CAPTAIN shows next image through microprojector	Completed
Test Case comments: None			

4.2.3.4.1 Measurement results

4.2.3.4.1.1 Resource utilisation & processing latency

CPU/RAM utilisation & processing latency

In Table 20 the information about the RAM and CPU consumption of the different services in BOX, based on its Raspberry Pi processing device, are presented. Even though the computational power is increased due to multiple recognitions by the camera due to the existence of many skeletons in the test laboratory, the resources' consumption is low.

Table 20: Resource utilisation (CAPT).

Per Service	RAM (%)	CPU (%)
m10-User-Authentication	6.8	0.1
audio-images-grabber	4.2	4.6
u04-captain-projection	9.4	0.6
c04-Motivation-Engine	2.5	0.1
Recommender	2.2	0.1
captain-Installer	1.2	0.1
s03-Face-Emotion	1.4	0.1
captain-ai	0.7	0.1
captain-device	0.7	0.1
captain-broker-bridge	0.5	0.1
s15-weather	0.8	0.1
m07-text-to-speech	0.6	0.1
m07-speech-to-text	1.5	0.1
c06-horn	0.4	0.1
user-model	1.3	0.1
c05-helm	1.6	0.1
u01-user-interface	0.6	0.1
MongoDB	1.4	0.7
EMQX Broker	1.1	0.1

In Table 21 the processing latency of skeleton analysis (i.e., detection of person's pose) and speech-to-text generation are presented after their execution in the BOX. The timestamps in the table depict one measurement out of many performed and the difference time reported in the third column is the average of the total runs. Specifically, the applied AI models are the posenet and the deepspeech, respectively.

We can see that the time to provide the pose detection is about 23 s and the speech-to-text generation about 7 s. The extended duration of the measurement results can be attributed to the concurrent execution of multiple processes on the device. Consequently, whenever a user is captured by the camera, the device initiates a fresh analysis of the photograph every 10 s. Similarly, the response time, from when the user issues a voice command to when the device processes it, is also affected by this simultaneous processing.

Table 21: Processing latency of different AI services in BOX (CAPT).

Service	Time Issued	Difference
Image Capture	16:07:21.788537	0 sec
Skeleton Analysis	16:07:33.633326	~23 sec
Command Capture (Audio)	13:27:09.570416	0 sec
Speech to Text	13:27:16.098150	~7 sec

4.2.3.5 Scenario E: Jetson AGX Orin evaluation with pose detection

Scenario E, presented in Table 22, focuses on the performance of NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin in terms of resource utilisation when pose detection is taken place. The posenet model is applied in our case. Specifically, CPU, GPU and RAM consumption measurements are provided and the inference latency among the image capture (resolution of 720 x720 pixels) and the extraction of pose is depicted. The processing is locally made in Orin, investigating its standalone performance and there is no need for any connectivity. This setup can be translated to the extreme edge of CC. In next phase of Task 3.4 different placements of Orin in CC will be investigated.

Table 22: Scenario E description (ICCS).

TC Setup:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ USB camera (720p) • Computation devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ GPU: NVIDIA Ampere architecture with 2048 NVIDIA CUDA cores and 64 Tensor cores ▪ CPU: 12-core Arm Cortex-A78AE v8.2 64-bit ▪ RAM: 32GB 256-bit LPDDR5 			
Tools Used: jetson-stats that is a package for monitoring and controlling NVIDIA jetson series			
Metering Process: USB camera is connected with ethernet to jetson orin and continuous video flows are inserted to the processing device			
Prerequisites	Operational camera and Jetson Orin		
Necessary test data	None		
Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Flash orin device with all computer vision libraries.	The libraries are appropriately installed.
	Step 2	Install a USB camera.	Camera communicates with orin.
	Step 3	Deploy jetson-inference.	Orin includes a set of deep learning inference models.
	Step 4	Configure posenet.	Posenet operates appropriately in orin.
	Step 5	Run inference on posenet with video stream from USB camera.	See the person’s pose in the monitor.

Test Case comments: None

4.2.3.5.1 Measurement results

4.2.3.5.1.1 Resource utilisation & processing latency

In the specific dry run testing the scope is to exclusively examine the performance of Orin when the pretrained posenet model is executed. To do that we collect video frames and their inferences are extracted. There are about 15300 frames with a total duration of 8.5 minutes of video considering that we have 30 frames per second (FPS). In Figure 34 the distributions of CPU, GPU, RAM and processing latencies are extracted. In the results we can see that the average inference latency is about 6ms, the GPU has average utilisation about 42%, CPU 12% and RAM 30.6%.

Figure 34: Resource utilization and inference latency distributions for posenet's execution in Orin (ICCS).

4.2.3.6 Scenario F: Jetson AGX Orin evaluation with speech to text generation

Scenario F, presented in Table 23, focuses on the performance of NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin in terms of resource utilisation when speech to text generation is taking place. Specifically, CPU, GPU and RAM consumption measurements are provided and the inference latency among the audio capture and the generation of text is

depicted. Similar to scenario E the processing is taking place in extreme edge of CC, however more placements will be investigated in next phase.

Table 23: Scenario F description (ICCS).

TC Setup:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computation devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ GPU: NVIDIA Ampere architecture with 2048 NVIDIA CUDA cores and 64 Tensor cores ▪ CPU: 12-core Arm Cortex-A78AE v8.2 64-bit ▪ RAM: 32GB 256-bit LPDDR5 			
Tools Used: jetson-stats that is a package for monitoring and controlling NVIDIA jetson series			
Metering Process: Pre-recorded audio stream is inserted to the processing device			
Prerequisites	Operational Jetson Orin		
Necessary test data	None		
Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Deploy jetson-inference	Orin includes a set of deep learning inference models
	Step 2	Deploy DeepSpeech	DeepSpeech operates appropriately in orin
	Step 3	Configure DeepSpeech to version 0.9.3	DeepSpeech version 0.9.3 is ready to be used in Orin
	Step 4	Run DeepSpeech with prerecorded audio stream	See the created text
Test Case comments: None			

4.2.3.6.1 Measurement results

4.2.3.6.1.1 Resource utilisation & processing latency

In this scenario, the pretrained deepspeech model is executed in Orin. This model takes as input voice samples, and convert them to text (we have tested prerecorded voice samples⁷). In our case about 600 samples have been used and are varied in duration (in seconds) with a distribution shown in Figure 35. Considering that the processing latency of an audio sample depends to its duration, we expect that larger samples will have larger values of processing time. Hence, to provide a more accurate analysis we separate them on two categories ‘Small’ and ‘Large’ as shown in Figure 36. The threshold of 9.5 s has been used for the separation of these classes.

In the results of Figure 36, we can see that the samples with larger duration have larger processing time, while the rest resources, based on this specific testing, are generally similar. Finally, we observe that the average latency is low, even if the samples are larger than 9.5 s in which the corresponding latency is about 2 s.

⁷ common_voice Datasets at Hugging Face

Figure 35: Latency distribution of samples that are used for deepspeech’s inference in Orin (ICCS).

	Time (s)	GPU(%)	CPU(%)	RAM(%)
Small	1.22	32.80	33.79	14.0
Large	2.15	25.41	33.75	14.0

Figure 36: Averaged values of processing latency and resource utilization of Orin’s performance in deepspeech (ICCS).

4.3 UC Conclusions

In terms of ICCS 5G connectivity infrastructure we can see that there is low performance mainly due to the hardware used. As a result, it’s planned to procure Amarisoft devices for the upcoming dry run testing in next phase of Task 3.4. Hence, the connectivity performance will be enhanced.

In terms of ICOM’s connectivity technologies, WiBAS™ G5 and UltraLink™ GX-80 provide throughput rates, system latency and versatile deployment capabilities that fully meet the network requirements of the diverse use cases in rural environments.

Finally, the data from the CAPTAIN Box measurements indicate that despite the involvement of numerous individuals in the test phase, there isn’t a significant strain on processing resources. However, it’s noted that response delays do occur, attributed primarily to the variety of services running concurrently and limited CPU resources.

In next phase’s integrated testing scenarios, we will investigate the system’s performance under the placement of processing devices in different layers of compute continuum considering in parallel the E2E connectivity solutions of ICCS and ICOM and more iteration tests will be done to the E2E infrastructure.

5 UC 3: Remote Community (UK)

5.1 Overview of the Service Supported by UC

In remote islands like Scilly, there are areas with no network coverage, making them 'blind spots'. Despite previous attempts to establish 4G and current efforts for 5G, complete coverage is still lacking. To effectively use sensors for soil, water, and weather data, reliable connectivity is crucial for informed decisions, such as irrigation. Scilly Organics, a small vegetable farm on the Isles of Scilly in the UK, will serve as a demonstration site for this project.

CAFA multirobot is designed for soil humidity measurement, obtaining better farm overviews, and ensuring a reliable data connection.

It integrates an advanced UGV (Unmanned Ground Vehicle) with an aerial drone.

- Aerial survey eliminates the frequent need for heavy machinery on fields.
- UGV reduces the amount of irrigation water.
- This eco-friendly approach protects the crop, minimizes field damage, and upholds the integrity of the soil.

5.2 Lab Testing Framework

5.2.1 Testing Scenarios

During the dry run testing, we are experimenting with two scenarios:

1. Computer vision and processing

One part of the CAFA multi-robot includes a drone equipped with an onboard camera system. The camera system is equipped with RGB and NIR sensors that capture aerial images. These images are compressed and sent to the robot's GPU device for nearly real-time processing. Aerial views provide a comprehensive overview of the farm. CAFA VideoLyzer software is used to identify plant health, early signs of drought, pests, and emerging diseases.

During dry run test, the tested concept is that the drone's software does not need to analyse data itself. Instead, it captures video, compresses it, and sends it to another computer where data analysis is performed. A computer simulating the drone's onboard computer is connected to a camera that streams the feed to another computer. The second computer runs CAFA VideoLyzer software, demonstrating how to detect objects. This can be seen in Figure 37.

We use the following devices for testing:

- 2 computers:
 - Ubuntu 22.04
 - Windows 11
- CAFA VideoLyzer software
- TRENDnet TEW-648UBM (Realtek RTL8188CUS)
- HIKVISION mini PTZ camera Model DS-2DE2A404IW-DE3

Figure 37: Computer vision and processing (CAFA).

2. Expanding the wireless network

One option for the CAFA multi-robot is to extend wireless network connectivity through a drone using a 5G router. The 5G Wi-Fi router provides data coverage within a 700-meter radius.

During the dry run test, the process of extending the wireless network through a 5G router is tested. Laptop 1 is connected over USB to a 4G/5G modem, which is connected to commercial 4G internet service provider (ISP). Laptop 1 creates a hotspot and shares its internet connection over USB Wi-Fi dongle. The tests below include the scenarios sharing Wi-Fi with a single and multiple clients. This can be seen in Figure 38.

Figure 38: Expanding the wireless network (CAFA).

We are using the following devices:

- 2 computers:

- Ubuntu 22.04
- Windows 11
- TRENDnet TEW-648UBM (Realtek RTL8188CUS)
- Quectel RM510Q-GL

5.2.2 Measured KPIs

The KPIs that have been examined in this first phase of dry run testing are presented in Table 24.

Table 24: Measured KPIs (CAFA).

KPIs	Segment	Description	Measuring process
Network throughput	Conn	Obtain measurements of the communication link bandwidth (in Mbps).	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 1 per device
Network latency	Conn	Measure network latency by pinging different points of the infrastructure (in sec).	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 1 per device
Jitter	Conn	Measure the variation in the delay of received packets (in sec).	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 1 per device
Processing throughput	Comp	Frequency of frames that are processed (production of inference) in one second (in FPS)	Duration: 3 min Number of executions: 2

5.2.3 Description of Tested Cases

The tests are performed in CAFA’s private infrastructure.

5.2.3.1 Scenario A: Computer vision and processing evaluation

As it has described in Section 5.2.1 (Computer vision and processing) and shown in Table 25, we are experimenting with the idea that the drone's software does not need to process data internally; instead, it captures video, reduces its size, and transmits it to another computer for data analysis. A computer emulating the onboard system of the drone is linked to a camera that continuously transmits its feed to another computer. The second computer operates CAFA VideoLyzer software, illustrating the process of object detection. The main goal is to demonstrate the capability of CAFA software to detect objects. In the second phase of Task 3.4 testing with a tethered drone is planned.

Table 25: Scenario A description (CAFA).

<p>TC Setup:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● End device: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ IP Camera ○ Laptop 1 ○ Laptop 2 ● Access device: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Wi-Fi TrendNet USB
--

- Computation device:
 - CAFA VideoLyzer

Tools Used: iperf, ping

Metering Process: Data from camera are inserted to CAFA VideoLyzer

Prerequisites None

Necessary test data None

Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Connect the camera to the laptop 1 (fixed IP)	No conflicts
	Step 2	Check connectivity to IP camera	Successful
	Step 3	Apply routing (IP camera to laptop 1 host)	Successful
	Step 4	Check connectivity to camera from laptop 2	Successful
	Step 5	Run Docker and containerised VideoLyzer	No errors
	Step 6	Run tests with CAFA VideoLyzer	Tests are successful

Test Case comments: None

5.2.3.1.1 Measurement results

5.2.3.1.1.1 Processing throughput

We use a camera with a resolution of 2560x1440 pixels. During the test Laptop 1 performs packet forwarding task. To detect the object, a CAFA VideoLyzer, presented in Figure 39, is applied and immediately indicates when the object is detected and provides a warning if it is not. The test is conducted with a helmet.

Figure 39: VideoLyzer configuration UI (CAFA).

In Figure 40, you can see how CAFA VideoLyzer detects an object. The CAFA software also displays the processing throughput in FPS. The FPS is approximately 1.8, regardless of the resolution used for the IP camera. The FPS is fluctuated between 1.6 and 1.9, with 50% of instances registering at 1.8 FPS, 25% at 1.9 FPS, and the remaining 25% ranging from 1.6 to 1.7 FPS.

Figure 40: (a) Object of interest not detected

(b) Object of interest detected (CAFA).

CAFA VideoLyzer successfully detects the presence and absence of the object, hence the test results are in line with our expectations that are the proof of CAFA software functionality.

5.2.3.2 Scenario B: Expanding the wireless network

As it has described in Section 5.2.1 (Expanding the wireless network), presented in Table 26, Laptop 1 is connected over USB to a 4G/5G modem, which is connected to commercial 4G ISP. Laptop 1 creates a hotspot and shares its internet connection over USB Wi-Fi dongle.

Table 26: Scenario B description (CAFA).

TC Setup:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Laptop 1 ○ Laptop 2 ○ Smartphone 1 ○ Smartphone 2 • Access devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Wi-Fi TrendNet USB ○ 4G/5G modem 	
Tools Used: Ookla’s speed app	
Metering Process: Wi-Fi is used by a single device and Wi-Fi is shared with multiple devices	
Prerequisites	Operational access WiFi network (access point) and compatible user equipment
Necessary test data	None
Activity	

Step Name	Description	Expected Result
Step 1	Connect 4G/5G modem with laptop 1 via USB	Device detected
Step 2	Establish the connection to 4G/5G and run bandwidth tests	Connection established; full bandwidth available for laptop 1
Step 3	Connect USB Wi-Fi dongle to laptop 1	Device detected
Step 4	Create Wi-Fi hotspot	Hotspot created and stable
Step 5	Connect laptop 2 to the hotspot and run bandwidth tests	Full bandwidth of 4G/5G or limited bandwidth due to WLAN dongle bottleneck
Step 6	Run the tests one by one and simultaneously using laptop 1, smartphone 1 and smartphone 2 as client devices.	Bandwidth reduced while all devices consumed the bandwidth simultaneously

Test Case comments: None

5.2.3.2.1 Measurement results

5.2.3.2.1.1 Network throughput & latency

Ookla's speed app is used to conduct the bandwidth test. The test results can be seen in Figure 41. Test 1 assesses the upload and download speeds with the modem connected to a public network, while test 2 gauges these speeds when Wi-Fi is shared with a single device. Finally, test 3 evaluates the impact on speeds when Wi-Fi is concurrently utilized by three devices. The download and upload columns are in Mbps and ping and jitter in ms.

Test	Device	Download (Mbps)	Upload (Mbps)	Ping (ms)	Jitter (ms)
Test 1	Laptop 1	184.6	14.8	17	-
Test 2	Smartphone 1	26.1	14.7	18	6.9
Test 3	Laptop 2	8.3	8.1	808	-
	Smartphone 1	15.7	8.7	21	6
	Smartphone 2	10.7	6.4	19	5.7

Figure 41: Network testing in 3 different scenarios (CAFA).

The test result indicates that the network throughput is good. Notably, the Ookla speedtest application for Windows did not record any jitter. The table indicates that the jitter value does not significantly change regardless of the test conducted.

It is found that when only one device is connected to the modem, the Wi-Fi sharing speed is higher. However, when Wi-Fi is shared among multiple devices, the Wi-Fi bandwidth is divided among them. In conclusion, the testing process has been executed successfully and the main bottleneck during the tests is the bandwidth limitation of the Wi-Fi dongle.

It has been noted that when a singular device is linked to the modem, the Wi-Fi reaches approximately 185 and 15 Mbps downlink/uplink respectively. When more devices are connected, due to resource competition such values highly decrease. In conclusion, the testing process has been executed successfully and the main bottleneck during the tests is the bandwidth limitation of the Wi-Fi dongle.

5.3 UC Conclusions

Laboratory tests provide us with a framework of measurements that we need to consider when organizing field trials. In the lab tests, we simulate actions with cameras and modems, which we plan to perform with the drone in the future. Onboard the drone, we have an RGB and NIR camera along with a high-capacity Wi-Fi router, enabling comprehensive farm surveys. The simulated camera experiment demonstrates that CAFA VideoLyzer allows for object detection. For the field tests, we need to further develop CAFA VideoLyzer to detect plant health and/or drought signs. Moreover, in next phase, where the integrated configuration will be investigated, more testing iterations will be executed in terms of the E2E infrastructure.

During the laboratory tests, we experiment with providing internet connectivity to multiple devices and discover that the Wi-Fi dongle bandwidth limitation is the primary bottleneck during the tests. To expand the wireless network, we require higher-performance hardware. For the field tests, we plan to expand the wireless network from the drone using a 5G router. The 5G Wi-Fi router will ensure data coverage within a 700-meter radius.

6 UC 4: Farming and Forestry (Lithuania)

6.1 Overview of the Service Supported by UC

Art21 has an extensive experience in drone operations for various purposes: tracking the wild boars' population, calculating the number of bison in a designated area by usage of a thermal camera. The soil sample results from the laboratory in combination with hyperspectral camera data obtained together with unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) operation, allows to train the AI model in different tasks. These are to predict the crop diseases, malnutrition and overflowing, in the forestry detect the damage caused by human (il)legal activities, damage to the flora by pests, or fire risk prevention. Traditional data transfer from the memory of SD card/hard drive is slow, cameras using the Wi-Fi network must connect to one – which is not available in the forest or field environment. Instead, mobile technology such as 5G can provide high throughput, low latency, and reliability needed for high-resolution thermal/hyperspectral and sensory data transfer live. 5G network operation in combination with the UAV will be tested over the forest environment in Lithuanian pilot.

6.2 Lab Testing Framework

6.2.1 Testing Scenarios

The initial scenario of this UC is to fly a UAV over the forest covered territory with a hyperspectral camera and transmit the data via a 5G router to the data storage server.

For the laboratory testing we need: router with capability to connect to 5G network. We have three major mobile network operators that provide 5G services. We will check the throughput capacities and time taken to transfer the file load. We will check the time taken by sending various size data files. The data files are randomly generated to build up the size, not taking into consideration the file content. Later the random file will be exchanged for a real data file from the hyperspectral camera. Usually, the size of the file is over 3 GB, and for the UAV flight we are looking to generate more than 18GB of files to transfer from the camera to the data storage server. The measurements include the 5G router and the camera. In terms of weight of devices that will be attached to the UAV and their influence on the UAV battery duration, this is planned to be tested in the field testing which will follow.

In the laboratory environment we will test the equipment on the constant power and on the UAV battery. Devices to be tested:

Computing device - NVIDIA Jetson Nano 2GB Developer Kit

1. UE Type: Micro computer
2. UE manufacturer: NVIDIA
3. UE SW version: Ubuntu 18.04.6 LTS aarch64 / kernel 4.9.337-tegra
4. Weight: 126 g

Far edge computing device - Synology NAS DiskStation DS420+

1. UE Type: Network-attached storage (NAS) Server
2. UE manufacturer: Synology
3. UE SW version: DSM 6.2.4-25556

4. Weight: N/A

5G router - Teltonika RUTX50

1. UE Type: industrial 5G router – DUAL SIM Card
2. UE manufacturer: Teltonika
3. UE SW version: RUTX_R_00.07.04.5
4. Weight: 710 g

Camera – Specim AFX10:

1. UE Type: Hyperspectral imaging camera
2. UE manufacturer: Specim
3. UE SW version: AFX10
4. Weight: 2.5 kg

UAV – DJI Matrice 600:

1. UE Type: Drone
2. UE manufacturer: DJI
3. UE version: Matrice 600;
4. Weight: 9.1 kg (with six TB47S batteries)
5. Batteries: 6x4500 mAh, or 6x5200 mAh, 22.2V or 26.3V

Figure 42 describes the connection model of the laboratory testing for two scenarios while the electricity source is constant (meaning electricity is infinite). NVIDIA Jetson storing the files of various sizes is connected to 5G router for data transfer via mobile networks to the remote NAS server. The other data source is hyperspectral camera (for field tests we might use thermal camera or RGB camera), which has an FTP inbuilt and is directly connected to 5G router for the data transfer via mobile network to the remote data server.

Figure 42: Scenarios with constant electricity supply execution diagram (ART21).

Figure 43: Scenarios with devices powered by the drone batteries execution diagram (ART21).

Figure 43 as in Figure 42 describes the testing scenario of the devices connected the same way, however the power supply in first case is constant, while in second is the drone batteries.

It is important to note that hyperspectral camera data is sensitive (it has to be consistent when final transfer is done), and large. Due to this we have a double SIM card router and are testing the file transfer protocols (FTP, SBA) to check which protocol works faster for file transfer and is more reliable. Python scripts are used throughout the dry-run tests. This allows us to collect the data automatically, store it in the database for future investigations and comparisons.

We use two SIM card router for several purposes.

1. To switch between the SIM cards automatically if the network is lost on one mobile network, and to continuously transfer the data with the other mobile network. Thus, a distinct Python script will be developed to manage the switching process for laboratory use, which is intended to be applied in field-testing scenarios.
2. The transferable files are cut into chunks to safeguard the file transfer success rate. Thus, switching of one mobile network and switching to another, should not restart the file transfer but resume the transfer when the network is restored, whether it is the same network in range or switched to the other available network.

For the laboratory setup, we will not be conducting drone flights with all the equipment attached. However, based on past experiences with flights using a hyperspectral camera, we've observed that the drone's flight duration typically ranges from 25 to 30 minutes. This range is important time frame for us to calculate the file transfer size, which will be applied in the field testing.

6.2.2 Measured KPIs

The KPIs that have been examined in this first phase of dry run testing are presented in

Table 27.

Table 27: Measured KPIs (ART21).

KPIs	Segment	Description	Measuring process
Network throughput	Conn	Obtain measurements of the communication link bandwidth (in Mbps).	Measure 2 network providers. Number of executions: 7 in 24 hours
Network latency	Conn	Measure network latency by pinging different points of the infrastructure (in sec).	Measure 2 network providers. Number of executions: 7 in 24 hours
Jitter	Conn	Measure the variation in the delay of received packets (in sec).	Measure 2 network providers. Number of executions: 7 in 24 hours
File Transfer Throughput/Time	Conn	Throughput (in Mbps)/Time (in sec) of transferring files from the Jetson device to NAS server	Duration: 30 minutes Every 3 hours Test different file size: Test_1KB.bin Test_10KB.bin Test_1MB.bin Test_10MB.bin Test_100MB.bin Test_1GB.bin Test_5GB.bin

6.2.3 Description of Tested Cases

The laboratory testing of the Lithuanian UC focuses on the data transfer and speed of mobile network. We are leaving the device weight and the drone lifting power and the time range for the field research. The weight of devices is affecting the drone performance time, and this is to be tested further in the field. Test cases differ by the files to be transferred (different devices connected) and the power supply (constant vs. drone batteries). The tests below are performed in ART21 private infrastructure.

6.2.3.1 Scenario A: Constant power supply with various size file transfer

Scenario A, presented in Table 28, is aiming to test the infrastructure of the devices, network and file transfer speed on the constant power supply. The expected result of the scenario is to get the files transferred to the endpoint (NAS) even if the network gets disconnected. Moreover, another target is to complete the file transfer whether the file size is 1MB or 5GB on the constant electricity power. The automated switches between the mobile network providers are tested, but we investigate below whether we are going forward with this implementation or simplify with only single SIM card with the best network provider choice.

Table 28: Scenario A description (ART21).

TC Setup: The setup will consist of the devices named in Figure 42 architecture. The edge device NVIDIA is storing the different file sizes. The biggest transfer is planned from the hyperspectral camera FTP server directly to data storage server NAS via Teltonika 5G router. (To test out the Teltonika RUTX50 5G router, we eliminate one of two data transfer protocols and eliminate 1 of three mobile network providers)

- Data stored in a computation device:
 - NVIDIA Jetson Nano 2GB Developer Kit (Ubuntu 18.04.6 LTS aarch64 / kernel 4.9.337-tegra, 5V constant power supply)
 - Specim AFX10 – a raw hyperspectral data file. Power input 10-30V

The data storage devices are connected to the 5G router with the LAN cables.

- Access device:
 - Teltonika RUTX50 (5G router – DUAL SIM Card, 9V constant power supply)
- Computation device:
 - Synology NAS DiskStation DS420+ (DSM 6.2.4-25556, power supply NA)

Tools Used: Internally created testing python tool for measuring file transfer, ping

Metering Process: metering process is handled using the internally created tool. This tool operates by systematically testing various configurations, essentially performing the task of transferring files from the computation device to the NAS server with a range of different variables, including:

- Different file sizes
 - Test_1KB.bin; 2. Test_10KB.bin; Test_1MB.bin; Test_10MB.bin; Test_100MB.bin; Test_1GB.bin
 - Test_5GB.bin (Hyperspectral camera file)
- Protocols
 1. SMB
 2. FTP
- Operators
 1. Bite LABAS
 2. TELE2
 3. Telia
- Times of the day – every 3rd hour

Prerequisites	Operational 5G network, Microcomputer Jetson, Specim AFX10, NAS		
Necessary test data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Test_1KB.bin 2. Test_10KB.bin 3. Test_1MB.bin 4. Test_10MB.bin 5. Test_100MB.bin 6. Test_1GB.bin 7. Test_5GB.bin (Hyperspectral imaging data file) <p>The files are stored internally on the NVIDIA Jetson Microcomputer and on the Specim AFX10 Hyperspectral cameras internal FTP server. With the python script it is initiated to transfer the file to the remote data server via the mobile network.</p>		
Activity	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Connecting the infrastructure. Jetson is connected with 5G router via LAN cable and Specim AFX10 hyperspectral camera is connected with 5G router via LAN cable.	No power shortage, the devices will work as usual.

		Devices are connected to constant power supply.	
Step 2		Speed test of Bite network.	5G – over 100Mbps download speed and up to 80 Mbps upload speed.
Step 3		Speed test of TELE2 network.	5G – over 100Mbps download speed and up to 80 Mbps upload speed.
Step 4		Speed test of Telia network.	5G – over 100Mbps download speed and up to 80 Mbps upload speed.
Step 5		Connecting to NAS.	Connected to remote server.
Step 6		Transferring the files from Jetson to NAS via mobile network: 1. Test_1KB.bin 2. Test_10KB.bin 3. Test_1MB.bin 4. Test_10MB.bin 5. Test_100MB.bin 6. Test_1GB.bin Transferring Specim AFX10 file: Test_5GB.bin	Complete data transfer to end data server.
Step 7		Repeat the steps 3-6 every 3 hours.	Check the network speed at various hours of the day – assuming that there are some peak hours during the day.
Step 8		Write all the data in a log file.	The log file created to store the data through the whole testing process.

Test Case comments:

The router is dual sim, so one sim card needs to be replaced manually in the device to run the testing of the network connectivity and speed test.

An important part is testing the file transfer protocol to make sure that the files reach the final destination – NAS in full, which means that the synchronization process is implemented, not to start the transfer while the router disconnects from the mobile network, but to pick up where the transfer is interrupted to continue on transferring the data in full.

In order to check that the network speeds are under the expected threshold, we have to check at a location where the 5G network is more stable and available at a wider range.

6.2.3.1.1 Measurement results

6.2.3.1.1.1 Network latency/throughput & File transferring

In the specific mobile router we could use two mobile operator SIM cards, which is why by testing the network upload/download speeds we have chosen to run further testing with Telia and Tele2 mobile networks,

eliminating Bite Labas. A complementary argument is that in the laboratory environment Bite Labas is not providing 5G network, and the UC is determined to test specifically the 5G network parameters.

Network latency

We have measured the minimum and the maximum latency for the configuration of the devices and we get the results averaged in Figure 44. Comparing both operators, we could state that Telia connectivity allows a much quicker response than Tele2. Besides, we observe a more stable connectivity with an average jitter of 8.12 ms of the RTT for Telia network and 31.83 ms for Tele2. An interesting jump on a specific hour during the measurement has occurred which does affect the measured results. Further investigation would be needed to find out the factor causing the latency jump for Tele2 at 10-19 00:00 hours. For testing purposes, we have decided to keep two SIM cards to test them on the field and plan to treat Tele2 as the backup mobile network provider, in case Telia will not cover certain testing area in the field testing.

Figure 44: The average latency measurement over the testing period (ART21).

Network throughput

The average DL throughput (called also as speed) for Tele2 is about 223 Mbps, and 255 Mbps for Telia, and UL speed average of Telia is about 84 Mbps and 60 Mbps for Tele2. Relatively it is not outstanding performance of the mobile network providers. However, it's a known fact that network speed varies based on location, which may introduce certain limitations during laboratory testing. There are no cell towers nearby, which gives us context on the network speed results obtained. Different locations on the field test are planned, so more extensive network speed tests will be performed outside the laboratory environment. The UL/DL speed consistency is visualised in the Figure 45 below.

Figure 45: Download/upload speed testing for two mobile network providers over the testing period (ART21).

File transfer measurements

Firstly, we should mention that we have done the testing on both FTP and SBA file transfer protocols. The performance on the file transfer success rate is even and as the hyperspectral camera has an inbuilt FTP server, to not complicate the system FTP file transfer protocol over the testing period is chosen. We have divided the working files into three categories: a) small files group b) medium files group and c) big files group. By transferring the data over the 5G network we achieve an average of about 4 Mbps file transfer speed for Telia, and 3.4 Mbps for Tele2. Figure 46 visualizes the speed drops at certain measurement time periods.

Figure 46: Mobile network file transfer speed in Mbps over the testing period (ART21).

To make it easier to understand what it means in transfer time, we have extracted the time it takes to transfer each file during the testing periods. The visualizations are split into small (Figure 47), medium (Figure 48) and large (Figure 49) file groups.

Figure 47: Mobile network file transfer speed in seconds over the testing period – small size file group (ART21).

Figure 48: Mobile network file transfer speed in seconds over the testing period – medium size file group (ART21).

Tele2 network takes on average about 1591 seconds (26.5 minutes) to transfer 5GB file and 1326 seconds (22.1 minutes) for Telia network to transfer 5GB file.

Figure 49: Mobile network file transfer speed in seconds over the testing period – large size file group (ART21).

This gives us an estimate that during the UAV flight of 25-30 minutes we would be able to gather 25-30 minutes of data but be able to transfer from 5-8 GB of data while in the flight. The rest of the transfer might be done when the drone lands, when the pilot is in transition, or the drone/infrastructure is connected to external power source/charger.

To measure further if the UAV battery has other performance nuances we have committed another scenario. An important note is that drone output power is 22.2 V or 26.3 V. It differs depending on the battery capacity, and it is important for the infrastructure, which will be discussed below.

6.2.3.2 Scenario B: UAVs battery supply with various size file transfer

We tested the planned infrastructure on the constant power and got the results that are described in the sections above. This scenario, presented in Table 29, aims to transfer the whole infrastructure and connect it to the drone battery and make it deployable anywhere. We know that while in flight the drone is affected by the weight of the devices attached, thus limiting the time of operation. Thus, the important focus of this scenario is to manage and connect all the devices to the drone and test the system under the battery power supply, being a drone (DJI Matrice 600), which differs from the constant supply. The expected result is the same as in the scenario A with the drone on the ground and the battery in use. The drone batteries are expected to last at least 12 hours of the testing period, which would be at least 6 testing rounds.

Table 29: Scenario B description (ART21).

TC Setup: The setup will consist of the devices named in Figure 43 architecture. The edge device NVIDIA is storing the different file sizes. The biggest transfer is planned from the Hyperspectral camera FTP server directly to data storage server NAS via Teltonika 5G router. (To test out the Teltonika RUTX50 5G router, we eliminate one of two data transfer protocols and eliminate 1 of three mobile network providers)

- Data stored in a computation device:
 - NVIDIA Jetson Nano 2GB Developer Kit (Ubuntu 18.04.6 LTS aarch64 / kernel 4.9.337-tegra, 5V constant power supply)
 - Specim AFX10 – a raw hyperspectral data file. Power input 10-30V

The data storage devices are connected to the 5G router with the LAN cables.

- Access device:

- Teltonika RUTX50 (5G router – DUAL SIM Card, 9V constant power supply)
- Computation device:
 - Synology NAS DiskStation DS420+ (DSM 6.2.4-25556, power supply NA)

Tools Used: Internally created testing tool for measuring file transfer, ping

Metering Process: metering process is handled using the internally created tool. This tool operates by systematically testing various configurations, essentially performing the task of transferring files from the computation device to the NAS server with a range of different variables, including:

- Different file sizes
 - Test_1KB.bin; Test_10KB.bin; Test_1MB.bin; Test_10MB.bin; Test_100MB.bin; Test_1GB.bin
 - Test_5GB.bin (Hyperspectral camera file)
- Data transfer protocols
 1. FTP
- Operators
 1. TELE2
 2. Telia

Times of the day – every 3rd hour

Prerequisites Operational 5G network, Microcomputer Jetson, NAS, DJI Matrice 600 (batteries)

Necessary test data

1. Test_1KB.bin
2. Test_10KB.bin
3. Test_1MB.bin
4. Test_10MB.bin
5. Test_100MB.bin
6. Test_1GB.bin
7. Test_5GB.bin (Hyperspectral imaging data file)

The files are stored internally on the NVIDIA Jetson Microcomputer and on the Specim AFX10 Hyperspectral cameras internal FTP server. With the python script it is initiated to transfer the file to the remote data server via the mobile network.

Activity

Step Name	Description	Expected Result
Step 1	Connecting the infrastructure. Jetson is connected to 5G router via WLAN cable and both devices are connected to drone (DJI Matrice 600) power supply.	No power shortage, the devices will work as usual for at least 12 hours on the drone battery.
Step 2	Speed test of TELE2 network.	5G – over 100Mbps download speed and up to 80Mbps upload speed.
Step 3	Speed test of Telia network.	5G – over 100 Mbps download speed and up to 80 Mbps upload speed.
Step 4	Connecting to NAS.	Connected to remote server.
Step 5	Transferring the files from Jetson to NAS via mobile network: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Test_1KB.bin b. Test_10KB.bin 	Full data transfer to the remote data server.

		c. Test_1MB.bin d. Test_10MB.bin e. Test_100MB.bin f. Test_1GB.bin Transferring Specim AFX10 file: Test_5GB.bin	
Step 6	Repeat the steps 2-5 every 3 hours.		Check the network speed at various hours of the day – assuming that there are some peak hours during the day.
Step 7	Write all the data in a log file.		The log file created to store the data through the whole testing process.

Test Case comments:
 The drone battery lasts quite long while the drone is not in operation. So big difference of the power supply is not expected, and the operations are carried out as usual.

6.2.3.2.1 Measurement results

6.2.3.2.1.1 Network latency/throughput & File transferring

We have performed the same test on the battery power input as it is done on the constant power supply. The power input to the router has changed from 9V (scenario A) to 24V, where we see different fluctuations in the graphs visualized.

Network latency

Tele2 shows a repetitive tendency to have a higher latency value at midnight hours, as we see in Figure 50. The average can be skewed by the transfer of bigger files, but this would need further investigation, although it does not affect the file transfer time, as the bigger files take not seconds rather minutes to transfer and the milliseconds do not make much of a difference for big file transfer. The RTT results while working on the drone battery are not significantly different from the constant power and are 32.65 for Tele2 and 9.12 for Telia.

Figure 50: The average latency measurement over the testing period on the battery power supply (ART21).

Network throughput

Under the battery power supply, we see that the download and upload speed consistency is more linear and similar to the constant power supply scenario Telia outperforms Tele2. Based on Figure 51 download speed averages about: Tele2 - 248, Telia - 255. Upload speed averages: Tele2 - 57.8, Telia - 89.9. While we see quite similar performance between the operators on the download speed, there is quite a big difference of the upload speed. Upload speed is the main focus of our UC.

Figure 51: Download/upload speed testing for two mobile network providers over the testing period (ART21).

File transfer measurements

The increased power supply to the router might cause a better efficiency as we see an increase of the file transfer speed. Tele2 – 3.39 and Telia – 4.24 as an average speed. The dynamics are visualized in the Figure 52 below.

Figure 52: File transfer speed on the battery power supply over the testing period (ART21).

Regarding the file transfer time, we do not see significant fluctuations. However, in the big file transfer group we see better numbers regarding camera data transfer. The latter has increased in speed which can reduce the time of transfer, meaning that more data can be transferred while in flight mode. The file transfer time of each group is presented in Figure 53, Figure 54 and Figure 55.

Figure 53: Mobile network file transfer speed in seconds over the testing period – small size file group (tested on battery) (ART21).

Figure 54: Mobile network file transfer speed in seconds over the testing period – medium size file group (tested on battery) (ART21).

Figure 55: Mobile network file transfer speed in seconds over the testing period – large size file group (tested on battery) (ART21).

6.3 UC Conclusions

The laboratory testing gives us the framework of measures that we need to consider while organising field testing. The most important is the file transfer size and speed. Except from the examined technical KPIs that test the main functionality, there are many other parameters that need consideration in case of the pilot. As noted in the beginning of the document several additional measures need to be considered: weight of the devices, aerodynamics, weather conditions, the position of the mobile network tower, data transfer while in the movement.

We have discarded Bite Labas network provider and will continue field testing on only two mobile network providers: Telia and Tele2. We keep in mind that Telia outperforms Tele2 on almost all measurements. Moreover, FTP is chosen to be the file transfer protocol and the drone battery, while not in-flight mode, can last over 24 hours for lab testing. Finally, to reduce the battery power consumption NVIDIA could be replaced with other small scale edge computing device such as Raspberry Pi with LAN cable connectivity solution.

7 UC 5: Aquaculture (Croatia)

7.1 Overview of the Service Supported by UC

Measuring water parameters is essential in aquaculture to maintain water quality, ensure public health, and sustainably manage water resources. Similarly, water quality measurements are crucial to environmental health monitoring and stability evaluation. The accuracy and reliability of measurements are critical for making informed decisions and taking appropriate actions to address water-related challenges. In most cases, water quality measurements have to be done periodically. Therefore, systems that can function and provide data autonomously are preferable. For such systems to function correctly, a stable connection has to be established, but this is not easy to achieve since the measuring sites tend to be placed in low connectivity areas, for example, offshore aquaculture farms and remote water sources. Traditional Wi-Fi or 5G technology does not provide the required functionality in such cases, and a low-power, long-range connectivity solution is needed. Considering this, a solution for remote and autonomous measurement of water quality parameters will be established using Long Range Wide Area Network (LoRaWAN) and satellite connectivity technologies in Croatia.

7.2 Lab Testing Framework

7.2.1 Testing Scenarios

The solution is comprised of two modules:

1. Water sensing equipment (water sensor, LoRaWAN transmitter, LoRaWAN gateway).
2. Satellite data transfer equipment.

These modules must be interconnected to form a single-integrated solution. Therefore, a computation device (edge-device) is used.

The water sensing module is crucial for the data collection. It gathers the data from aquatic remote environments and sends it to the shore for analysis. This module comprises the water sensor, the LoRaWAN transmitter and gateway, and the edge unit. The water sensor, located at the measuring site, typically offshore, collects water quality parameters. The specific parameters that are measured can vary and depend on the sensors that the end-user purchases and installs. The sensors are connected to the LoRaWAN transmitter through a cable, which is used to transfer the data to the transmitter.

Once the data reaches the transmitter, it is sent to a LoRaWAN gateway (using the EU868 band). The LoRaWAN gateway can be quite far from the measuring site, within the limits of LoRaWAN's connection range. Multiple transmitters can send data to the same LoRaWAN gateway. In this way, the LoRaWAN gateway is like a central data hub, collecting data from different measuring sites over a wide area. The LoRaWAN gateway is connected to the edge device, aggregating and storing the data and metadata.

The satellite data transfer module makes the data accessible to the end user. This module comprises the edge device and the satellite data transport equipment (provided by Astrocst). When a connection with the satellite is established, the data is sent to the database (using the L band). The frequency of the data transfer depends on the satellite revisiting time and how often it needs to be sent.

The application programming interface (API) takes the data from the database, and this is graphically visualised to the end users via a dedicated platform. They can use any standard internet connection to log in and view the collected information. This system makes it easy to get essential insights from the data collected by our water-

sensing modules. The end-users can work in any environment (for example, in the comfort of their home) and do not need to travel to the measuring site.

The simplified schematic diagram of the data collection and transfer system is provided in Figure 56.

Figure 56: Schematic diagram of the Croatian UC (BENCO).

The central aspect ensuring the continuous and smooth operation of the system is the connection stability between all parts of the system. Therefore, the system status is defined by several parameters:

1. Sending status of the LoRaWAN devices. The time since the last packet of data was received is measured. This should be no less than the set acquisition period. The acquisition period is between 1-2 minutes, depending on the device.
2. The time duration since the LoRaWAN gateway synchronised the time with the edge device. Typically, this time should be less than 10 min.
3. LoRaWAN gateway status at the last data sync.
5. Signal strength of LoRaWAN devices.
6. Last satellite contact time and signal strength.

7.2.2 Measured KPIs

The KPIs that have been examined in this first phase of dry run testing are presented in Table 30.

Table 30: Measured KPIs (BENCO).

KPIs	Segment	Description	Measuring process
Response Time	Conn-Comp	Time between request generated, and service response received (in sec)	Number of executions: 3 Duration 3 days
Jitter	Conn-Comp	Measure the variation in the delay of received packets (in sec).	Number of executions: 3 Duration 3 days
Resource Utilisation	Comp	Monitor CPU and RAM usage of the NUC.	Number of executions: 3 Duration 3 days

7.2.3 Description of Tested Cases

The goal of the tests is to evaluate the performance of isolated network modules of the system. The system is split into two segments – LoRaWAN and satellite data transfer modules. The testing of each module is regarded as a new scenario where technologies included in the module are connected and tested, and the corresponding KPIs are evaluated. The tests below are performed in BENCO private infrastructure.

7.2.3.1 Scenario A: LoRaWAN and computation segment evaluation

Scenario A, presented in Table 31, is dedicated to investigate the functionality of the LoRaWAN connectivity module used in the developed system for the remote water parameter evaluation system. During the test case, connectivity characteristics and resource consumption parameters are evaluated. This test case proves that the water sensor can efficiently transfer the data through LoRaWAN to the edge device.

Table 31: Scenario A description (BENCO).

TC Setup:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End Devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salinity sensor <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Manufacturer: Aqualabo ○ Type: Submerged, stationary • Manta probe – multiple sensors installed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Manufacturer: Eureka Water Probes ○ Type: Submerged, stationary • Access Devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aqualabo AquaMod <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Type: LoRaWAN Transmission Module ○ Manufacturer: Aqualabo ○ SW version: Aqualabo software version 1.5 ○ Transmission frequency: 2 minutes • Libelium Plug and Sense <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Type: LoRaWAN Transmission Module ○ Manufacturer: Libelium ○ FW version: Internal firmware ○ Transmission frequency: delay of 30 seconds after each transfer • Gemtek WLRGFM-100 gateway <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Type: LoRaWAN Gateway ○ Manufacturer: Gemtec • Computation Devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intel NUC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Manufacturer: Intel ○ Characteristics: Intel i5-6260U / 16 GB RAM / 512GB 	
Tools Used: Inside tools (python program) for estimating KPI values.	
Metering Process:	
During testing procedure, the setup will be tested, and relative parameters of the water sensing module will be evaluated using built-in programs for data capturing. The test will be run for an extended period of time (3 days), to estimate the average values of network performance.	
Prerequisites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All parts of the module are operational.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LoRaWAN communication is established 			
Necessary test data	Data from the salinity sensor.			
Activity				
		Step Name	Description	Expected Result
	Step 1	Start the module.	All module parts are operational.	
	Step 2	Establish the LoRaWAN gateway and edge device (Intel NUC) connection.	The LoRaWAN gateway is connected to the edge unit.	
	Step 3	Verify the connection between the LoRaWAN transmitter and gateway.	Connection is established.	
	Step 4	Synchronise the time between the edge unit and the end device.	The time synchronisation is successful.	
	Step 5	Verify the water sensor status.	The water sensor is online.	
	Step 6	Collect and transfer the water sensor data to the edge unit.	Data is transferred successfully.	
Step 7	Estimate different metrics in terms of network and system performance.	The metrics correspond to the KPIs.		
Test Case comments: None				

7.2.3.1.1 Measurement results

Testing is carried out over three days to evaluate the performance and reliability of the developed system's water-sensing module. Three separate tests were conducted where water quality data was collected using a water sensor, and the data was sent via LoRaWAN to the edge device (Intel NUC). The collected data is presented as recorded, or the calculated parameters' values are shown. Data collection and evaluation of the characteristic parameters are carried out using a built-in Python program.

7.2.3.1.1.1 Data volume & response time testing

Data volume

Due to the fact that the amount of data, as we have sensors' monitoring data, is minimal, we use bytes and not bps. We have on average 30 bytes every 2 min for Aqualabo sensors and 27 bytes every 45 s for Libelium sensors.

E2E response time

E2E response time is estimated as time taken for the data to be transferred from the LoRaWAN gateway to the edge device. The edge device sends a confirmation signal upon receiving the data package. As can be observed in Figure 57 the average value of the E2E response time is around 2.2 s. The jitter is calculated from the data of E2E response time as their variance and the jitter of the water sensing module is estimated to be 0.83 s.

Figure 57: Results of the E2E response time testing (BENCO).

7.2.3.1.2 Resource utilisation

The CPU and RAM usage are estimated. These are related to the edge device (NUC) and is not high since the sensor data does not require any resource-heavy computations. On average, the values of these parameters are respectively 13.1 % (CPU) and 900 MB (RAM). The results gathered during testing are shown in Figure 58.

Figure 58: Data of the resource utilisation - CPU, RAM, of the edge device within the water sensing module (BENCO).

7.2.3.2 Scenario B: Satellite data transfer evaluation

Scenario B, presented in Table 32, is dedicated to investigate the functionality and performance of the satellite connectivity module used in the developed system. During the test case, connectivity characteristics and resource consumption parameters are evaluated. This test case proves the successful establishment of satellite communication and data transfer.

Table 32: Scenario B description (BENCO).

TC Setup:

- Transport Devices:

- Astrocast Astronode S
 - Type: A bidirectional satellite communication module with a serial interface
 - Manufacturer: Astrocast
 - Firmware Version: 2.8.0
- Computation Devices:
 - Intel NUC
 - Type: A bidirectional satellite communication module with a serial interface
 - Manufacturer: Intel
 - Characteristics: Intel i5-6260U / 16 GB RAM / 512GB

Tools Used: Inside tools (python program) for estimating KPI values.

Metering Process:

During the testing procedure, the setup will be tested, and the relative parameters of the water-sensing module will be evaluated using built-in programs for data capturing. The test will be run for an extended period of time (3 days), to estimate the average values of network performance.

Prerequisites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All parts of the satellite module are operational. • Satellite communication is established
Necessary test data	Data from the salinity sensor.

	Step Name	Description	Expected Result
Activity	Step 1	Start the module.	All module parts are operational.
	Step 2	Establish the connection between the Astrocast equipment and the edge device (Intel NUC).	Connection is established.
	Step 3	Establish a connection with the satellite.	Connection with the satellite is established.
	Step 4	Send the data to the database via satellite connection.	Data transfer is successful.
	Step 5	Compute the revisiting time and plan the next data transfer.	The data transfer schedule is prepared.
	Step 6	Visualise the received data in the GUI.	Data is shown in the GUI.
	Step 7	Estimate different metrics in terms of network and system performance.	The metrics correspond to the KPIs.

Test Case comments: Much of the KPI values are determined only by the satellite communication parameters. Satellite communication is available for a certain and limited period of time. Therefore, service availability of the whole module is determined by the satellite communication part.

7.2.3.2.1 Measurement results

Testing was carried out over three days to evaluate the performance and reliability of the developed system's satellite data transfer module. Three separate tests were conducted where previously collected water quality

data was packed and sent from the edge device (Intel NUC) via Astrocast’s satellite network to the database. Data is then taken for the database and is visualised on the Grafana dashboard. As with scenario A, data collection and evaluation of the characteristic parameters are carried out using a built-in Python program.

7.2.3.2.1.1 Data volume & response time testing

Data volume

The amount of data that the satellite data transfer module of the developed system can send is solely determined by the maximum data amount that can be transferred via the satellite network itself. The amount of data in one packet that can be transferred by Astrocast’s satellite network is fixed. The maximum volume of the data packet that can be sent via Astrocast’s satellite network cannot exceed 160 bytes. Taking this into account the system is now designed in such a way that the satellite data transfer module sends a packet with a volume of 153 bytes.

E2E response time

E2E response time is estimated as time taken for the data to be transferred from the edge device via satellite network to the database. The corresponding time data is shown in the Figure 59. As can be observed the E2E response time has a high value with an average of around 305 minutes. As already mentioned, this is determined by the fact that satellite data transfer is not possible most of the time. Since the satellite is orbiting the earth, the communication is available only for some periods within the day, when the Astrocast device is in contact with a satellite. As in the scenario A, the jitter for the satellite data transfer module is around 31 minutes.

Figure 59: E2E response time data collected during satellite data transfer module (BENCO).

7.2.3.2.1.2 Resource utilisation

The evaluation of the resource utilisation of the satellite communication module is performed in the same manner as in the previous scenario. The CPU and RAM usage of the edge device is even lower. On average, the values of CPU and RAM parameters are respectively 8 % (CPU) and 600 MB (RAM). However, it should be noted that resource usage is somewhat dependent on the amount of data coming in from the water sensors. The more data that is coming in, the more data packets have to be sent. This takes more time and resources. The results gathered during testing are shown in Figure 60.

Figure 60: Data of the resource utilisation - CPU, RAM, of the edge device within the satellite data transfer module (BENCO).

7.3 UC Conclusions

The laboratory testing gives us the framework of measures that we need to consider while organising field testing. Two modules of the system - the water sensing module (LoRaWAN and computation segment) and the satellite data transfer module are tested. Since the communication in both modules is straightforward – data is transferred between two designated ends (transmitter and receiver) of the system, the main parameters that determine the performance of the system and measured are E2E response time and resource consumption of the computation segment.

The test shows that the water sensing module is a reliable part of the system. The performance of the system is stable throughout the long durations of the tests. The processing segment does not require a lot of resources since the data coming in from the water sensors is straightforward – numerical information. Thus, no advanced processing is required. Even though, different models (depending on the manufacturer) of the sensors can in part make an influence of the performance, since the period of the data transfer might be different.

The satellite data transfer module on the other hand, is a more complicated part of the system. This complexity comes from the fact that data can be transferred via satellite only when the communication between the ground-based and lower orbit-based equipment is established. Communication can only be established at certain points in time which are determined by the position of the satellites. Such a requirement creates a limitation of data transfer and a high delay. When compared with standard connectivity options (Wi-Fi, 4G, etc.) such a delay might seem not worth the system implementation. However, if the standard connectivity options are not available, this system proves to be very useful since it does not require a lot of resources and infrastructure to be implemented.

Data testing shows that when implemented, it should be expected that the performance of the full system will be highly influenced by the satellite data transfer.

8 Conclusions

This deliverable constitutes the first version of the 'System integration and dry-run testing feedback report' (M15). In this deliverable, based on the access, transport and computation parts that are examined in KFT, various connectivity and computation devices are tested under different technical KPIs in the laboratory environment. The tested equipment is originated by the UCs' scope, but also further connectivity measurements are provided, such as public networks in rural areas from I2CAT. The content of this deliverable provides useful insights for the applied equipment and the system topology configurations that will be applied in living labs of WP5.

The second deliverable 'System integration and dry-run testing feedback report', due M27, will be an updated version of the current deliverable. It will provide the testing of E2E systems, combining the isolated devices into integrated configurations. Moreover, these more complex testing scenarios will be validated with additional testing iterations, where it is necessary, and more KPIs in the test cases that are feasible, such as power consumption of devices and service's availability and reliability.